

CALIPER
Gender Equality in STEM Research

Linking Research & Innovation for
Gender Equality

D2.3 GEPs

WP2- Design and development of
customized GEP

Version: 1.0

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Executive Summary

The report presents the first versions of the GEPs (Gender Equality Plans) elaborated by the consortium's partners to foster institutional change for gender equality in their own organizations. Introductory chapters 1 and 2 account for the design process followed by partners to involve both internal and external stakeholders as well as the support provided by Smart Venice as gender expert organization for the consortium.

The elaboration of the GEPs represents the last step of a process started in T2.1 with the development of institutional change scenarios and continued in T2.2 with the identification of key external stakeholders belonging to the partners' innovation ecosystem, the organization of the dialogues and the setup of R&I Hubs. Within T2.3, after the consultation with the middle and top management and a second set of dialogues with the external stakeholders, the GEPs' actions have been designed and included in an overall document later submitted to the body in charge for its approval. 9 GEPs have been elaborated, in which 182 actions have been included, 42 of which are collaborative actions involving 176 external stakeholders.

Chapter 3 shows an overview of the actions included in all GEPs, trying to point out some emerging trends and commonalities within the consortium. Overall, all areas of intervention (human resources, institutional governance, research/research funding, teaching, transfer to market, communication, students service, sexual harassment and intersectionality) have been addressed by the GEPs actions, with clear differences between RPOs and RFOs. The analysis shows how the areas which have been addressed at most are the ones of human resources, research/research funding and institutional governance.

Chapters from 4 onward present a summarized description of each GEP, together with the list of measures included in the Plans in their versions as of the 30th of June 2021, while the final official approval steps of the documents, except for one partner, is still under finalization. These individual chapters contain a link to the full versions of the GEPs, collected in an online repository that is constantly updated as the final approval takes place.

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full form
RPOs	Research Performing Organizations
RFOs	Research Funding Organizations
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Math
R&I	Research & Innovation
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
ERA	European Research Area
GE	Gender Equality
WG	Working group

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose, scope, structure of the deliverable

The present document collects the GEPs elaborated by the 9 partner organizations, which will be implemented starting from M19 (July 2021).

The deliverable is structured with an initial chapter explaining the process followed by partners in the GEPs' design, as well as the tools and the support provided by Smart Venice within the process. Chapter 3 gives an overview of the GEPs' actions, distinguishing between actions involving only internal stakeholders (e.g. human resources departments, decision making bodies, academic staff, students, etc.) and collaborative actions with external stakeholders belonging to the partners' innovation ecosystems. The analysis provided points out common trends and features of such synergies. From Chapter 4 to Chapter 12, the GEPs designed by each partner are presented, briefly listing the measures included, and the links where to find the full version of the GEPs are provided. A final chapter with concluding remarks is also included.

1.2 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

The present document is the conclusive deliverable of WP2 "Design and development of customized GEPs" and is therefore connected with the previous WP2 tasks related to the "Development of strategic change scenarios" (T2.1) and "Organization of Multi Stakeholder dialogues" (T2.2).

The GEPs elaborated by partners are organized based on the areas of intervention as defined in D1.1 "Internal and external assessment methodologies and guidelines".

The document also represents the starting point of the Implementation phase (WP3) and it is strictly connected with WP4 "Monitoring and Evaluation", since monitoring and evaluation activities will be based on the actions included in the GEPs and the identified indicators.

2 GEP design: process, support and tools

The design of the GEP has started in T2.1 with the development of institutional change scenarios. Within this task led by ULB, partners reflected on the findings of the internal and external assessment (WP1) and develop three implementation scenarios (with minimal, maximal, and intermediate estimated levels of resistances). In each scenario, challenges, problems and possible solutions were identified for each area of intervention: human resources, institutional governance, institutional communication, research (funding), teaching, students' services, sexual harassment, intersectionality and transfer to market.

In T2.2, partners identified key external stakeholders belonging to their national and regional innovation ecosystem in order to set up the CALIPER Research & Innovation Hubs. A first set of dialogues with the stakeholders part of the hubs¹ was organized in order to present them the results of the internal and external assessment, the main challenges and possible solutions as well as to identify joint strategies and opportunities. For guiding partners on how to involve R&I Hubs stakeholders in the GEPs Design phase, SV designed a dedicated training course (February 23rd and 25th) inviting GEPs Working Groups members and with the participation of Advisory Board members: the two sessions were aimed at operationalising results from D1.3, and to run hands-on exercises on how to identify potential common challenges with a different type of stakeholders and envisage possible joint actions, based on role-playing with fictional characters (personas).

In the frame of T2.3 "GEPs design and development", Smart Venice supported partners through different actions:

- The elaboration of ad hoc guidelines (see Annex I);
- The preparation of a GEP's template;
- The preparation of a repository of measures/actions;
- 9 Bilateral calls.

As far as the guidelines are concerned, they were aimed at guiding partners in the different steps of the design phase as well at ensuring the application of a collaborative approach in the GEP's design. The figure below shows the different steps followed by partners towards the GEP's design.

Figure 1: Steps of the process towards the GEP's design

The first step partners were recommended to take was the elaboration of a **concept map** for each thematic area (e.g. human resources, institutional governance, teaching, etc.) and eventually for each sub-area if need be, including findings of the scenarios elaborated in T2.1 and the results of the dialogues with the R&I Hubs (T2.2). The aim of the concept maps was to highlight problems and challenges per each topic, the

¹ For further information about the R&I Hubs, consult D2.2 "Reporting results of multi-stakeholder dialogues".

related identified solutions, pointing out possible collaborative actions with external stakeholders. Detailed instructions were provided to partners for the elaboration of the concept maps.

The concept maps were then used during the **consultations with the top and middle managers** in order to present them the results of the previous steps. In particular, the consultation with the top managers was aimed at discussing and finalizing the Institution’s Gender Equality strategy and overall priorities. The results fed into a dedicated report shared internally with consortium members for follow up on the process.

Once the overall priorities and the strategy were defined, parallel meetings with middle management and other internal actors/actresses involved in the GEP design as well as in the actions were organized. The purpose of these meetings was to identify and analyse a set of feasible solutions/actions per each area. The results of the meetings were included in a dedicated report. The main conclusions of these meetings were reported to Smart Venice for follow-up purposes.

Within the consultations with the middle management, by adopting a collaborative approach, or in parallel, the GEP’s working groups started the design of the different actions to be included in the GEP by using the **log-frame** provided in the above mentioned guidelines. The log-frame was elaborated in the frame of the Evaluation and Monitoring Methodology (WP4) and made available to partners in the GEPs design phase in order to ensure continuity and coherence between the design and the evaluation of the design itself which will take place at a later stage. The structure of the log-frame is reported below.

Figure 2: Structure of the log-frame from D.4.1

A log-frame was requested to be filled per each action identified. The aforementioned guidelines provided detailed indications about what to report under each section.

The last step before the release of the first draft of the GEP was the organization of the **second set of dialogues with the R&I Hubs**. The aim of reconvening the Hubs was to expose stakeholders to the overall identified strategy and action plan, or excerpts of those, and further discuss with them about joint actions to be included in the GEP. Further recommendations about how to organize the mentioned dialogues were provided within the guidelines, with particular reference to the duration and the structure of the sessions. These second dialogues were also aimed at involving those stakeholders that could not take part in the first dialogues. Partners were also recommended to organize follow-up meetings (bilateral or in smaller groups) with those stakeholders with which they were going to start joint actions already in the frame of the first GEP's iteration. Each partner had to include at least 2 collaborative actions in their GEPs.

The last phase of the process concerned the elaboration of the **GEP** using the structure provided by Smart Venice (Annex E of the guidelines). The template includes an introductory part aimed at presenting the overall Gender Equality Strategy and the key priority areas and different sections for each area (Human Resources, Institutional Governance, Institutional Communication, Research, Teaching, Transfer to Market, Student Services, Sexual Harassment, Intersectionality) targeted by the identified measures. Under each area a brief description of the existing situation in terms of gender inequalities is requested, in order to make the document readable and understandable also to those who did not follow the entire previous gender assessment and design phases. Each section is also structured in sub-sections related to the different sub-areas. For each one of the identified actions, a log-frame as in Figure 2 had to be filled in. A specific section is dedicated to collaborative actions, while the last one to an overall gantt chart.

The above-mentioned guidelines provided also with a list of deadlines corresponding to the different steps, which is reported below:

Steps	Implementation of the activity	Elaboration of the reports/supporting documents to send to Smart Venice
Consultation with top management	mid-April	30th of April (report of the meeting, Annex A)
Consultation with middle management	end of April/beginning of May	31st of May (report of the meetings and log-frames, Annex B and C)
Dialogues with R&I Hub	Mid-End of May	31st of May (report of the dialogues and log-frames of collaborative actions, Annex C and D)
First version of the GEP	7th of June	7th of June (Annex E)
Finalization of the GEP and approval by the body in charge	June	30th of June (final GEP, Annex E)

Table 1: Deadlines within the GEPs design process

Another tool elaborated by Smart Venice in order to support partners in the GEP's design process consists of a **repository of resources** containing practical examples of actions that have been implemented by other RPOs and RFOs in the frame of structural change processes towards gender equality. The repository is composed by two tables: the first one includes a list of around 70 measures divided per area, while the second one a list of relevant resources (toolkits, deliverables, publications, ppt presentations, etc.). A brief description and information about the project/source they refer, the link for further information, the indication of which kind of partner (RPO or RFO) could adopt the indicated action are also provided. The repository of actions has inspired partners in the design of the measures to be included in their GEPs.

The repository, which will be periodically updated, is available at this [link](#).

Bilateral calls have also taken place between Smart Venice and each partner in order to discuss about any issues, challenges or resistances encountered within the process and receive strategic guidance and suggestions, as well as solve doubts about how to fill the different sections of the GEP template provided.

Finally, by the 7th of June, partners shared a first draft of the GEP with Smart Venice, which reviewed the documents including comments and suggestions about how to improve them.

Being an official institutional document, each GEP underwent an approval process by the Institution's middle and the top management. At the time the present Deliverable is submitted, not all the GEPs have concluded the approval *iter*. Indeed, as it will be specified in sections 4 onwards (introduction of the different GEPs) some of them are still in the process, having been approved by the middle management (e.g. the deans) but not by the top management (e.g. the general assembly or the general director). For each GEP, it will be specified at which step of the approval process it is, when the approval by top management is expected and if any adjustments with respect to the current version of the document are envisaged.

The current versions of the GEPs are included in the following [Google Drive folder](#). They will be replaced with the final versions, once they will be approved by the correspondent authorities and/or decision-making bodies.

3 GEPs: an overview

3.1 GEPs' actions and main areas of interventions

Overall, partners have inserted 182 actions in their GEPs, including 42 collaborative actions with external stakeholders that are detailed in the next paragraph. As already mentioned in the introductory chapter (chapter 1) of the present document, the actions introduced in the GEPs are organized based on the areas of intervention as defined in D1.1 “Internal and external assessment methodologies and guidelines” and summarized here below.

Area/topics of intervention	Description
Human resources	It includes units/departments in charge of recruitment/retention & career progression and work-life balance/wellbeing services or provisions.
Institutional governance	This area is mainly related to the decision-making structures and bodies as well as governance processes featuring each organization.
Institutional communication	It concerns the use of gender sensitive language in the organization's documents as well as in the communication channels and materials.
Research	This area refers to integrating gender into the content of research within all scientific fields and components (design, delivery and research communication).
Research funding	It represents the core activity of Research Funding Organizations, encompassing processes of preparing calls for proposals and setting evaluation criteria, to organizing evaluation processes leading to selections and decisions on funding allocation.
Students services	It mainly consisting in students' recruitment and post graduate counselling.
Teaching	It is related to curricula design and preparation, but also includes interaction and communication with students as well students' assessment/evaluation activities in order to understand whether gender bias is present at any stages.
Transfer to market (or third mission)	This area concerns the role of research institution to engage with societal needs and market demands by linking its activities with its own socio-economic context.
Sexual harassment	It is related to the existence of actions and policies aimed at addressing and preventing sexual harassment and gender based violence in the organization.
Intersectionality	It related to measures where gender is taken into account in conjunction with other kinds of discriminations/structural inequalities.

As it is visible from the figure below (figure 3), among the actions not involving external stakeholders, the area in which partners have included more actions is human resources, with 36 actions. This is not surprising as it can also be considered as the most encompassing one, since it includes different sub-topics, all of them of high relevance (e.g. recruitment and selection, working conditions and work-life balance, career progression, etc.).

The second most targeted area is research/research funding. It is worth to underline that some partners have for internal reasons grouped actions related to the topics of research, teaching and students service (and also transfer to market/third mission in the case of UNILE) under one overall area. However, for the purpose of the analysis, the actions have been split in the different areas according to their specific content. In addition, still for the purpose of the analysis, in some cases, actions have been re-organized in different areas based on their content. Indeed, even though partners have been provided with a template and definitions of the different areas², they have adapted the classification of the actions according to their own structures and peculiarities.

Also the area of institutional governance counts a notable share of the actions (26), some of which can be considered as structural measures (e.g. the set up of Gender Equality Bodies or similar units/services).

On the other side, the areas with less actions are transfer to market (5), students services (4) and intersectionality (6). As far as transfer to market is concerned, 4 partners have included actions (MTF STU, UEFISCDI, UNILE and NTUA), while with reference to students services, three partners have addressed such area in their GEPs (FER UZG, IRB and ULB). As far as intersectionality is concerned, four partners (IRB, UNILE, NTUA and SRNSFG) have included specific actions targeting such area in specific (the creation of an intersectional data collection system, the implementation of an alias career for transgender students, and raising awareness activities), while one partner (ULB) has integrated it as a transversal topic in most of the actions, foreseeing specific indicators aimed at measuring the impact of the actions from an intersectional point of view. It is worth to mention that, even though included in the area of students services, the action regarding the establishment of a career alias for transgender students foreseen by a partner (UNILE) is strictly connected with the intersectionality area.

Human resources, institutional governance, research and communication are the areas in which all partners have included at least one action.

² See D1.1 about the methodology for the internal and external assessment for more details.

Figure 3: GEPs' actions per topic

Obviously and due to their peculiar functions, no actions have been included by RFOs on teaching and students services.

The duration of the implementation of the actions varies according to the type of actions, some of them taking a few months, other years. In all cases, their implementation will be finalized by the end of the second GEP's iteration (August 2023).

The actions included in the partners' GEPs will be analysed and detailed from chapter 4 onwards. This deliverable lists the actions included in the GEPs' versions available as of the 30th of June 2021 (or 1st July 2021). In some cases, actions have been slightly reformulated.

3.2 Collaborative actions

The CALIPER project adopts a multi-stakeholder and quadruple helix approach leveraging internal change also through the activation of synergies with external stakeholders. As a result of the external assessment carried out in the frame of WP1, all partners have identified suitable stakeholders to be involved in the R&I Hubs, which have been set up within WP2. Two dialogues with external stakeholders have been organized by partners in T2.2 and T2.3, so that stakeholders have been involved already in the GEP's design phase. The main objective of the dialogues was to identify common challenges, to develop a portfolio of strategic opportunities and, more important, to examine possible collaborative actions. In particular, according to the guidelines for T2.3 (see Annex I) during the second dialogues, the focus was to present to the stakeholders the identified internal strategy and action plan and to further discuss about joint and so called "collaborative" actions to be included in the GEP. Collaborative actions are the ones organized and implemented in collaboration with external stakeholders (belonging to academia, business sector, civil society and government/public sector), each of them having specific roles in the implementation.

All the partners have included such actions in their GEPs. In total, the 9 GEPs count of 42 collaborative actions with 176 stakeholders. As it can be observed from the figure below, collaborative actions refer to 7 areas of intervention, and some of them even tackle different areas at the same time. The the great majority are related to research and communication.

Figure 4: Collaborative actions per area

Collaborative actions within the research area include for instance, the elaboration and dissemination of guidelines on the inclusion of the gender dimension into STEM research and development of collaborative research projects (RFOs), or the set up of awards/prizes for female scientists and collaborations in the process of creating evaluation criteria for future calls which take into consideration the gender dimension (RFOs).

As far as communication is concerned, collaborative actions entail the organization of raising awareness events/conferences focused on the topic of gender or dedicated to female researchers, and the creation of networks focused on women and STEM.

In the area of human resources, developing common recruitment protocols and measures in order to avoid bias in selection and evaluation processes is a collaborative action on which forces are joined mainly with other RPOs, while within the area of sexual harassment actions are mainly related to training and raising awareness activities on the topic. The same kind of actions are foreseen with reference to the teaching area.

Within the transfer to market area it is worth to mention the development of a system to monitor the evolution of women's achievements in this sector, while in the area of students services collaborative efforts tend to be mainly aimed at attracting new students. Also it is worth to point out that most partners have included the organization of the FemTech event (Task 5.2 of the GA) as a collaborative action, in some cases under "research", in other under "students service" or "transfer to market", depending on the emphasis to one or the other area they intend to give when designing the event itself. With reference to the kind of stakeholders involved in the collaborative actions included in the GEPs, the following figures shows that 38% (66) of the stakeholders belong to the academic sector, followed by government/public sector counting for 24% of the stakeholders (43), the business sector represented by 22% (39) and finally civil society with 16% (28) of the stakeholders.

Figure 5: Stakeholders' types in collaborative actions

From an overall analysis of the collaborative actions included in the GEPs, some trends and commonalities are emerging as far as what stakeholders tend to be more engaged in what type of action if the kind of stakeholders involved and the type of actions. In particular, as expected, actions within the research and teaching areas mainly involve stakeholders belonging to the academic sector (universities and other research centers), while those under transfer to market and human resources tend to involve both stakeholders of the academia and of the business sector. Actions within other areas such as communications and sexual harassment tend to involve stakeholders from academia, business sector and civil society, while actions related to students' services also involve the public sector, schools included.

4 ULB's GEP

The Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB) in Belgium has designed a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) for its two STEM faculties, the Faculty of Sciences and the Brussels School of Engineering.

The document was presented and unanimously approved by the Faculty Council of the Polytechnic school of Brussels on the 23rd June 2021 and by the Faculty Council of the Faculty of Sciences on the 1st July 2021. The final step will be to present the GEP to ULB's Academic Council for its approval (planned for the end of August) and the signature of the Plan by the Rector and the two STEM Deans (Faculty of sciences and Brussels School of Engineering – BSE). The latest version of the GEP is downloadable at this [link](#).

The strategy that the GEP adopts is twofold: it focuses on *both* STEM-specific situations to improve *and* on transversal problems that are addressed at STEM faculty level.

Human resources, students and students services, and governance are the three main priority areas of the GEP. Accordingly, most of the structural measures included in the GEP are situated in these areas. However, other areas are also included in the Plan. Indeed, research, teaching, students' services, communication, sexism and sexual harassment are also important areas addressed by the GEP. Hence, the GEP comprises measures aimed at integrating a gender dimension in STEM research and teaching contents and practices, at promoting inclusive communication practices, and at preventing discrimination and harassment. Measures in these "secondary" domains support change in the three main priority areas of the GEP - human resources, students and students services, and governance. With some exceptions, the actions in these areas are mainly 'soft' measures aimed at raising awareness, disseminating knowledge and facilitating access to services.

Only two of the areas initially analysed are not directly covered in the GEP: women's participation in transfer to market and intersectionality. The first one is indirectly addressed by means of the actions on human resources, since the main problem is the under-representation of female STEM academics. The question of spinoffs and entrepreneurship is not addressed in the GEP because it is linked to specific institutional dynamics and processes that extend beyond gender issues and are out of the scope of this GEP. The second one, intersectionality, is not considered as an area in itself. Within this GEP, intersectionality is considered a transversal strategy to design all actions of the Plan. Hence, the GEP adopts a gender+ strategy: gender remains the main contemplated type of inequality but its interaction with other sources of inequality and grounds of discrimination is considered in the design and implementation of the GEP measures. When possible, intersectional indicators have been added to the measures.

The following figure shows the ULB's GEP key priority areas with the number of actions per area.

Figure 6: ULB's GEP Key Priority Areas

Overall, 14 “non-collaborative” actions have been included in the GEP, while 6 are the collaborative actions which are related to research, students service and sexual harassment areas. The external stakeholders involved are 13, mainly (7 out of 13) belonging to the academia sector or public sector (5 out of 13).

Here below all the actions included in the ULB’s GEP, in its version as at the 1st of July 2021, are listed.

Human Resources

N.	Measures/actions	Objective (short term)	Timeframe of implementation
1	Toolkit to avoid unconscious biases in recruitment	To provide STEM recruitment and selection committees with HR solutions and good practices in recruitment to avoid gender unconscious biases	September 2021 – January 2022
2	Action-oriented study ‘Affirmative actions for academic recruitment’	To assess the feasibility and relevance of affirmative actions for recruitment and hiring at the University	February – June 2022
3	Action-oriented study ‘Correction standard for career breaks due to childcare leaves’	To assess the feasibility of a correction standard for career breaks due to childcare leaves in selection procedures for academic vacancies	September 2022 – January 2023
4	Action-oriented study ‘Extension of post-doctoral contracts for the duration of maternity, paternity and/or parental leave’	To assess the feasibility (in terms of type of contract and budget) of post-doctoral contract extension for the duration of childcare leaves	February – June 2023

Institutional governance

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of
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			implementation
5	Gender+ commission in STEM faculties	To institutionalize gender+ policy at STEM faculty level	September - December 2021 (establishment)
6	Creation and collection of gender indicators at STEM department/service/discipline level	To collect gender disaggregated data within STEM disciplines regarding the gender composition of the academic, scientific and student bodies	January – April 2022
7	Proposal for a gender-balanced participation in Advisory Boards	To promote a gender-balanced composition of advisory bodies at the institutional level	October 2021 – May 2022

Research

N.	Measures/actions	Objective (short-term)	Timeframe of implementation
8	Gender target in STEM PhD juries	To define and set a gender target at each STEM faculty to promote gender balance in the composition of STEM PhD juries	October 2021 – May 2022

Teaching

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
9	Guide on gender-sensitive teaching	To finalize and disseminate a guide on gender-sensitive teaching	July 2021- March 2022
10	Consultation for an explicit integration of a sex/gender+ perspective into STEM curriculum competency frameworks	To assess the feasibility and define the specific formulation to explicitly integrate a sex/gender+ and diversity perspective into STEM curriculum competency frameworks	September 2021 – June 2022

Students services

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
11	Consultation for a new science and technology training for future secondary school teachers	To examine the possibility of designing a new interdisciplinary science and technology qualification program to teach at upper secondary level for science teachers	October 2021 – June 2022

Communication

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
12	Hands-on training on inclusive communication for STEM webpages administrators	To equip webpages administrators with a range of tools to implement inclusive communication	October 2021 – January 2022
13	Review and update of the communication of current STEM websites	To use inclusive communication in STEM faculties websites	February 2022-June 2022
14	Dedicated webpage for the gender+ measures of STEM faculties	To make visible the gender+ policy at the STEM faculties	October – December 2021

Collaborative actions

n.	Collaborative action	Area	Interest expressed	Collaboration confirmed	Timeframe
1	Dissemination of guideline on the inclusion of the sex/gender dimension in (STEM) research	Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women & Sciences Committee (6 French-speaking universities + RFO) 	TBC	February – June 2022
2	Exhibition 'Sex/gender+ in STEM research'	Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women & Sciences Committee (6 French-speaking universities + RFO) (TBC) City of Brussels 	TBC	May 2022 – May 2023
3	Gender technical support to mainstream the gender+ perspective in ULB science outreach activities	Students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> equal.brussels VIVAQUA 	TBC	July 2021 – June 2022
4	Joint ULB-g4g FemTech event	Students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> g4g equal.brussels (TBC) City of Brussels (secondary schools) VIVAQUA 	Yes	Between December 2021 and January 2022

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> University of Namur 		
5	Advertising of training on discrimination and harassment targeting STEM faculty authorities and departments/services leaders	Sexism and harassment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UNIA Institut pour l'égalité des femmes et des hommes - IEFH 	TBC	From the availability of the training onwards (especially once a year from May to July – transition period)
6	Permanent poster campaign	Sexism and harassment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> City of Brussels 	TBC	September 2022 – February 2023

The actions will be implemented from July 2021 to June 2023.

5 IRB's GEP

The GEP elaborated by the Institute for Research in Biomedicine (IRB) of Barcelona (Spain) was designed with the involvement of internal and external stakeholders. Their participation was encouraged to contribute to the following points:

1. Promote equality and diversity.
2. Contribute in creating a structural framework to overcome identified challenges and specific situations that were identified as result of the assessment phase of the CALIPER project.
3. Create a working group that allowed a multi-dimensional, multi target and multi-method approach.

Through the Plan, IRB intends to implement new actions in order to support and promote equality and diversity, providing a broader vision with the goal of driving structural changes in this matter. Actions will be used as a tool to create systematic standards for future with the objective of achieving the integration of gender perspective at all levels of the institute.

The version of the document as at the 30th of June 2021, which is available at this [link](#), has not been approved by some of the IRB Barcelona bodies (Directorate, Faculty and Equality Commission), therefore it is still subject to changes and corrections.

The GEP intends to create long-term solutions to identified challenges within the institute and provide continuity to existing efforts and initiatives already set in place. The main strategy of the Institute can be summarized in two general objectives and eleven specific objectives.

General Objectives:

- Make the principle of equality a distinctive feature of IRB.
- Integrate the gender perspective at all levels of the organization and in all institutional policies.

Specific Objectives:

- Design strategies that integrate the principle of equal opportunities into the organization's culture.
- Ensure equal, inclusive and non-sexist communication.
- Facilitate access to information and documentation, as well as internal communication channels for the entire workforce.
- Guarantee neutral and equal selection and promotion processes, working towards a balanced presence in the different professional groups and levels.
- Ensure the application of a remuneration policy and a neutral professional classification.
- Eliminate any provision, measure or labor practice that involves discriminatory treatment in relation to the type of contract or workday.
- Guarantee equal opportunities in access, training and career development for the entire workforce
- To be a benchmark entity in the scientific sector on equality and diversity.
- Carry out gender awareness actions for IRB workforce.
- Work towards an organization of working time that favors the reconciliation of personal, family and work life.
- Ensure the applications of effective policies to prevent harassment in the organization.

The GEP includes 21 actions in the following areas: human resources, institutional governance, institutional communication, research, transfer to market, student services (renamed as "Young Scientists"), sexual/gender harassment, and intersectionality.

Figure 7: IRB's GEP Key Priority Areas

Special emphasis has been given to the human resources area and in particular to measures aimed at ensuring equal pay and work-life balance to IRB's employees. On the side of institutional governance, the adoption of a mentoring program in order to foster career progression is worth to mention, as well as the promotion of a gender-sensitive language through different measures within the communication area. The integration of the gender dimension in research is also tackled in the plan through the inclusion of training sessions targeting the IRB scientific community. Concerning the actions included in the students' services area, they are aimed at reinforcing the awareness of new students on equality and diversity. In the area of sexual harassment, IRB plans to review and update the existing protocol against sexual harassment and train employees on this issue. The action included on intersectionality is aimed at creating awareness and construct a critical perspective on the topic.

3 collaborative actions are included in this version of the plan and are mainly related to the areas of human resources and transfer to market. External stakeholders involved are mainly belonging to academia and civil society.

Here below all the actions included in the IRB's GEP, in its version as at the 30th of July 2021, are listed.

Human Resources

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
1	Review, update and disseminate existing recruitment policies and guidelines, assuring that the documentation has a gender-sensitive approach.	Broaden knowledge of recruitment measures, policies and protocols on the part of the IRB Barcelona community	September – November 2021
2	Conduct a salary audit regarding equal pay	Ensure equal treatment and non-discrimination among men and women with regard to pay	October 2021- December 2022
3	Plan and develop training actions to raise awareness of the	Make work-life balance effective at IRB Barcelona, enhancing an institutional	January 2022- Continuous

	importance of work-life balance and promote a pro-conciliation leadership management model.	culture in which the promotion and support of conciliation are highly valued.	
4	Develop a Parental Leave Guide.	Provide support to parents-to-be and encourage men to take parental leave.	November 2021- January 2022
5	Develop a Work-Life Balance Guide	Inform about the existing work-life balance measures at IRB Barcelona.	February 2022- June 2022

Institutional governance

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
6	Mentoring Programme: To promote career progression.	Provide a guidance method for career progression reflecting commitment to the career development of women .	September 2021- Continuous
7	Consolidate and disseminate Group Leader selection protocol.	Increase awareness of the protocol, its advantages, and the results of its application.	September 2021- Continuous
8	Prepare an internal regulation to govern the Equality and Diversity Committee.	Provide a document regulating the functioning of the Equality and Diversity Committee and the roles of its members.	January 2022- July 2022

Research

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
9	Offer training sessions on the integration of the gender dimension into research.	Understand the importance of gender dimension in research and innovation.	April 2022- Continuous
10	Create and consolidate a protocol for planning and developing internal seminars, promoting and assuring the	Assure that the speakers who give seminars at the Institute are chosen considering the gender perspective.	January 2022- Continuous

	participation of female speakers.		
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Students services (Young Scientists)

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
11	Reinforce equality and diversity topics in onboarding sessions.	Give all newcomers a general overview of efforts made at IRB Barcelona e in matters pertaining to quality and diversity.	October 2021- Continuous
12	Integrate gender perspective training in transversal PhD programme.	Include a mandatory course to inform about existing initiatives addressing equality and diversity.	September 2023-June 2024

Communication

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
13	Internal and external visibility to the new Gender Equality Plan.	Raise institutional awareness of efforts to be made in matters pertaining to equality and diversity.	September 2021- Continuous
14	Manual/guidelines on inclusive language (English, Spanish, and Catalan)	Include gender sensitivity in internal/external communications.	July 2022- December 2022
15	Checklist/guidelines for posting and checking material on the Institute's social media channels.	Provide a guide to ensure the gender sensitivity of external communication on social media platforms.	July 2022- December 2022
16	Advanced training on inclusive language.	Integrate an inclusive (gender, diversity, intersectional) approach into oral and written communications and apply the recommendations for diverse and inclusive communication.	January 2022- March 2022
17	Institutional engagement in equality and diversity topics (videos, institutional equality day, printed materials, among others).	Give greater visibility to the efforts made by IRB Barcelona with respect to equality and diversity topics.	September 2021- Continuous

Sexism and gender harassment

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
18	Internal training on Sexual & Gender Harassment.	Increase awareness and capacity to prevent and recognise sexual harassment.	March 2022-Continuous
19	Protocol on Sexual Harassment.	Prevent and eradicate behaviours related to sexual and gender harassment.	September 2021- January 2022

Intersectionality

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
20	Awareness campaigns on Intersectionality.	Construct a critical perspective on intersectional topics, providing the grounds to rethink everyday practices.	January 2022-Continuous
21	Advance training session on gender and diversity topics for members of the Equality Commission.	Provide an advance perspective on the concept of equality and diversity.	January 2022-July 2023

Collaborative actions

n.	Collaborative action	Area	Stakeholders involved	Timeframe
1	Introduce measures to avoid bias in selection and evaluation processes.	Human Resources	CERCA	September 2021-Continuous
2	Develop a system to monitor the evolution of women in transfer to market	Transfer to Market	Universidad de Santiago de Compostela Innovatia 8.3	TBD
3	Engage with the innovation ecosystems: CALIPER FemTech Events.	Transfer to Market	R+I HUB members	TBD

6 UNILE's GEP

The GEP elaborated by the University of Salento (Italy) on the frame of the CALIPER project can rely on different and multiple actions already set up at the University among which there are such as:

- The appointment of a pro-rector for Gender Policies.
- The appointment of an Ombudsperson, outside the University, to address mobbing or harassment cases.
- The CUG³ activities.
- The strategic plan of the pro-rector for Gender Policies.
- The first UniSalento Gender Budget
- A web page on the UniSalento website dedicated to Gender Equality Policies⁴
- Seminars and lessons on “Gender Issues”, within the UniSalento+ Project, an inter- and transdisciplinary teaching approach on strategic issues in the study courses of the University of Salento⁵.
- The participation of the pro-rector for Gender Policies in the CRUI (the Committee of Italian Rectors) Technical Committee on Gender Policies, and in the team defining guidelines for GEPs in Italian Universities.

At the Italian national level a huge work is currently underway at the CRUI's level for the formulation of general guidelines for the implementation of GEPs in the Public Universities, therefore, the re-design phase foreseen in the frame of the CALIPER project will also include an alignment with the mentioned guidelines.

The version of the GEP as at the 30th of June is available at the following [link](#). It will undergo 4 approval steps:

1. approval by the Vice-Rector for Gender Policies
2. approval by the Rector and the General Manager
3. approval by the Senate
4. approval by the Board of Directors.

In view of the technical time required to complete the above mentioned steps, UNILE is expected to finalized the approval process by the end of October or early November 2021.

The current version of the GEP tackles 8 areas, with 27 actions. The most crucial area is the one concerning the management of human resources, and in particular its sub-areas of recruitment, retention and career progression and family-work reconciliation policies. Indeed, in order to reduce the existing significant horizontal and vertical segregation and increase female visibility and representation in governance are included in the present plan.

In order to achieve these objectives, it is considered crucial to support internal decision-making processes towards gender equity, through the creation of a dedicated entity (“coordination table”) and a dedicated team, which can oversee and ensure cooperation between the different areas of the GEP, gather needs and proposals, but also elaborate updated data on the progress made.

³ “Comitato Unico di Garanzia” (“Joint Guarantee Committee”), which main role is to ensure, in the context of public work, gender equality and equal opportunities, eliminating all forms of psychological moral violence and direct and indirect discrimination relating to gender and age.

⁴ <https://www.unisalento.it/ateneo/politiche-di-genere>

⁵ <https://www.unisalento.it/-/rete-questioni-di-genere->

Concrete measures have also been designed to monitor the other areas considered strategic for the promotion of gender equality within the University:

- measures related to research, teaching and transfer to market;
- measures about counteracting any forms of bullying and discrimination, with an intersectional approach;
- and finally, measures related to the transversal area of institutional communication, to be exploited to ensure information on actions, tools and services related to gender policies and equal opportunities and to promote their use and dissemination.

Figure 8: UNILE's GEP Key Priority Areas

As far as collaborative actions are concerned, 9 actions are included in the GEP addressing all the areas and mainly involving stakeholders belonging to the academic sector and civil society with the aim of lobbying towards gender equality policies in national bodies.

Here below all the actions included in the UNILE's GEP in its version as at the 1st of July 2021 are listed.

Human Resources

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
1	Briefing dedicated to recruitment committees for sensibilization and promotion of unbiased recruitment procedures	Promoting gender diversity in scientific careers	June 2021-Oct 2022
2	Actions aimed at the organizational well-being and the quality of work environment	Promotion of Unisalento's mission as a fair and gender inclusive training and working environment	June 2021-June 2022
3	Actions aimed at reconciling life	Support policies for those with family	June 2021-sept 2022

	/ work	responsibilities	
4	Elaboration and implementation of an “offer and request” online desk for the identification and support of work life balance measures	Support policies for those with family responsibilities	June 2021-Sept 2022
5	Guidance to early career researchers to favour retention	Promoting gender diversity in scientific careers	June 2021-Oct 2022
6	Support for equal opportunities in careers	Promoting gender diversity in scientific careers	June 2021-Oct 2022
7	Enhancement of gender diversity in technical-administrative careers	Promoting gender diversity in scientific careers	June 2021-Oct 2022

Institutional governance

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
8	Annual review of Gender Budget (BDG)	Promotion of Unisalento's mission as a fair and gender inclusive training and working environment	June 2022
9	Coordination group and dedicated team	Implementation of more consistent and effective strategies for the promotion of Unisalento's mission as a fair and gender inclusive training and working environment	Jun 2021 – Jun 2022
10	Rebalancing careers: governance interventions to increase fair visibility and representativeness	Implementing effective support actions to increase the number of underrepresented individuals in the highest roles of academic careers, such as, for example, women in scientific disciplines.	Jun 2021 – Jun 2022.
11	Consultations involving students and staff	Definition of the objectives to be implemented and the plan of action through collaboration between the components of the University.	Jun 2021 – Jun 2022

Research

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
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12	Promotion and organisation of scientific gender related workshops and events	Introducing gender perspectives in teaching and research.	Oct 2021- end of the project
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Teaching

N.	Measures/actions	Objective (short term)	Timeframe of implementation
13	Interdisciplinary seminars on gender issues and feasibility study about the introduction of a gender course	Introducing gender perspectives in teaching and research.	Oct 2021 – Nov 2022
14	Differentiated training for students and staff on gender related issues	Introducing gender perspectives in teaching and careers	Jan 2022-Dec 2022

Transfer to market/third mission

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
15	Opening a medical practice for staff and students in the technological campus, in collaboration with the Italian NHS.	Strengthening collaborations with the local institution. Enhancing attention to the students' health.	Oct 2021 – Jun 2022
16	Collaborations with equality bodies and professional associations at regional, national and European level networks	Strengthening the networks of local and non-local ecosystems	Jun 2021 – end of the project

Communication

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
17	Web page dedicated to the activities of the Vice-Rector for Gender Policies with documents, regulations, news on initiatives and actions in progress related to gender policies (Gender Budget and other relevant studies and analyses)	Ensuring information on actions, tools and services related to gender policies and equal opportunities and promoting their use and dissemination	June 2021- July 2021
18	Series of seminars on language and stereotypes in the media	Promoting greater awareness of gender	Sept 2021 – Dec 2021

	and social media, aimed at the academic community and the local area (professional bodies, institutions, etc.).	sensitive language use	
19	University Guidelines for the use of gender sensitive language.	Recognition and modification of existing practices (administrative forms, University website, regulations, other forms of communication)	Jan 2022 – Mar 2022
20	Conscious word - Staff training on the implementation of the Guidelines, and dissemination of the Guidelines throughout the university, with the active involvement of the university structures	Promoting the use of gender-sensitive institutional language	April 2022 – Jun 2022
21	Implementation of the Guidelines in forms, website and other forms of official communication	Revision of institutional documents to use gender-sensitive language	April 2022 – Jun 2022

Sexual harassment

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
22	Publicising and informing about the rules and the role of the CUG (<i>Comitato Unico di Garanzia CUG - joint guarantee committee</i>) and of the OmbudPerson and access to their services (including information material).	Promoting initiatives to detect situations of harassment, bullying and discrimination, also with reference to the student component	Sept 2021 – Jun 2022
23	Regulation on combating sexual harassment, bullying and discrimination in the workplace and in education	Adopt specific protection and safeguard measures	Nov 2021 – Dic 2021
24	Publication of annual reports by the OmbudPerson and subsequent preparation of a document analysing and planning interventions	Raise awareness on harassment, bullying and discrimination, also with reference to the student component	Sept 2021 – Jun 2022
25	Cycle of meetings dedicated to the topic of mobbing and sexual harassment with a function of basic knowledge of these phenomena, their dynamics and	Promoting a specific action of information to students and academic personnel, in collaboration with student associations, on harassment, mobbing	Sept 2021 – Jun 2022

	consequences	and related topics	
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Intersectionality

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
26	Alias career for transgender students	Promoting gender diversity in scientific careers	Jun 2021-Oct 2022
27	Initiatives to raise awareness of the phenomenon of discrimination among students in relation to gender, age, disability, ethnic origin, language, political opinions, sexual orientation	Promoting a specific action of information to students, in collaboration with student associations, on harassment, mobbing and related topics	Sept 2021 – Jun 2022

Collaborative actions

n.	Collaborative action	Area	Stakeholders involved
1	Collaboration for the introduction of the option of suspending the research grant during maternity leave	Human resources	Research centers and other universities
2	Extension of the university career evaluation period to 18 months for each pregnancy	Human resources	Research centers and other universities
3	Establishment of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • funding for participation in conferences in the post-doctoral period; • prizes for gender-oriented research projects. • mentoring and role models to support female researchers in presenting projects. 	Research	Research centers and other universities
4	Lectures in the program of UniSalentoPLUS on GEP	Teaching	Civil society, government, academia
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities in schools aimed at promoting a gender culture • scholarships for participation in specific degree courses (especially STEM) for the less represented gender • a more objective guidance service, based on the real aptitudes of the students 	Students services and to students	Civil society, government, academia

6	Actions for the gender-sensitive communication and language	Communication	Civil society, government, academia
7	Collaboration for identification of actions already in place in equality bodies of stakeholders and in NGOs which try to prevent violence against women	Sexism and sexual harassment	Civil society, industry government, academia
8	Prizes for research projects that develop gender-oriented products	Transfer to ma	Civil society, industry, academia
9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consolidation of childcare services in conjunction with regional and municipal services. • Agreements with educational structures in the area for staff living far from the existing nursery 	Human resources	Civil society, government

7 FER UZG's GEP

The GEP elaborated by the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing of the University of Zagreb in Croatia (FER UZG) has not been officially approved yet by the decision-making bodies of the Faculty. The procedure of approval of the Gender Equality Plan will undergo two main steps:

1. approval from the Dean,
2. approval from the Faculty Council.

As at the 30th of June, the document has been submitted to the Dean. The Dean may suggest adjustments of the draft, therefore minor or major revisions of this draft are possible. After the approval by the Dean, the draft will undergo a public discussion before seeking approval from the Faculty Council. The draft will be disseminated to all employees, and they will have the opportunity to familiarize themselves with the content of the draft. During a month-long public discussion, all employees of FER will have the opportunity to provide their suggestions and comments on the draft to the faculty management. Each received suggestion will be taken into consideration and addressed. If appropriate, the draft will be adjusted, therefore minor or major revisions of this draft are possible.

The tentative dates of the two approval steps are the followings:

1. July 23rd 2021 for approval from the Dean,
2. September 15th 2021 for the approval from the Faculty Council.

The latest version of the document is available at the present [link](#).

The measures included in the GEP are based on the results of the research study on gender equality at FER and in the local and national environment in which the Faculty operates.

The general strategies of the GEP are:

- the plan is in compliance with the faculty, university and national legal acts;
- the plan responds to the challenges identified in the research study and takes into account the internal capacities of FER;
- the plan is open to employees, students and external stakeholders;
- the plan allows changes in line with new findings.

As visible in the figure below, the areas covered by the plan are: human resources, institutional governance, research, institutional communication, sexual harassment and student services. The areas of research and teaching have been merged in one.

Figure 9: FER's GEP Key Priority Areas

10 “non-collaborative” actions have been included in the plan. With reference to the area of human resources, particular attention has been put in the adoption of measures aiming at attracting and retaining female researchers. About institutional governance, worth to mention is the establishment of a gender equality body encharged of disseminating and revising the GEP, monitoring the state of gender equality and preparing annual reports. Other measures included in the GEP concerns the study/analysis of legal documents in order to revise language practices to be more gender sensitive. In the areas of research and teaching, measures are maily aimed at integrating the gender dimension in both activities. The GEP also includes an action for attracting new female students under the students service area, as well as measures to strengthen and improve the existing system for fighting sexual harassment and discrimination.

4 collaborative actions have been also included involving 14 stakeholders belonging to the 4 sectors and are related to the area of teaching, governance, transfer to market and students service.

Here below all the actions included in the FER’s GEP in its version as at the 30th June 2021 are listed.

Human Resources

N.	Measures/actions	Objective
1	Strengthening the availability of existing measures and services for employees	This measure aims to maintain equal access to information for all employees and will strengthen communication and information channels towards employees. FER continues to support employees in reconciling work and private life and ensuring equal rights for all employees in selection, employment, work and professional development.
2	Attracting and retaining female researchers	This measure envisages the systematic collection of data and their analysis with the aim of better understanding why people decide to leave higher education and research. The new findings will be the basis for the introduction of new measures to ensure, to the extent possible, the attraction and retention of talented researchers.
3	Support for researchers after parental leave	This priority measure aims to support top researchers when they return to work after parental leave. The implementation of this measure will contribute to strengthening of security and self-confidence of female researchers, increase in job satisfaction and greater motivation to invest in

		their professional growth. The institution will provide equal opportunities for career advancement for women and men and enable a better work-life balance of employees. In the long run, the implementation of this measure will contribute to the increase of institutional research productivity and innovation capacity.
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Institutional governance

N.	Measures/actions	Objective
4	Establishment of a gender equality body	<p>The measure envisages the establishment of adequate administrative mechanisms in the field of gender equality. The implementation of this measure will contribute to strengthening the culture of equality at the institution.</p> <p>The main responsibilities of the body are dissemination and revision of the gender equality plan, monitoring the state of gender equality, collecting relevant data and preparing annual reports on gender equality, organizing training on gender equality for employees, promoting equal treatment of women and men and active participation in relevant activities at FER and at the University of Zagreb.</p>
5	Reporting on the state of gender equality	The implementation of this measure will establish appropriate administrative mechanisms for data collection and analysis and reporting on the state of gender equality. Furthermore, institutional awareness and commitment to a culture of equality will be raised.

Research

N.	Measures/actions	Objective (short-term)
6	Promotional campaign on gender integration of the gender dimension in research	The measure envisages the design and implementation of a communication and promotional campaign on scientific results and research groups that successfully integrate the gender dimension in research. In the long run, this measure contributes to strengthening institutional quality, competitiveness and innovation, and interdisciplinarity in research.

Students services

N.	Measures/actions	Objective
7	Strengthening the availability of existing services for students	This measure aims to actively strengthen equal access to information for all students and strengthen communication and information channels to students. The aim of the measure is to retain and support talented female students. In the long run, the implementation of this measure will also affect the share of women in the scientific and teaching staff, which is correlated with the share of female students.

Communication

N.	Measures/actions	Objective
8	Establishment of a specialized digital communication channel	The measure envisages the establishment of a digital communication and information channel dedicated to the dissemination of relevant information in the field of gender equality and the promotion of female researchers. The implementation of this measure will give visibility to the institutional commitment of the gender equality and contribute to transparency.
9	Gender sensitive language in legal documents	The measure envisages the revision of language practices in legal documents and the implementation of the conclusions of the analysis. The aim is to better understand the institutional legal documentation and the experiences of the individuals to whom these documents are addressed. The implementation of this measure will ensure equal professional conditions for all researchers and increase the motivation of women to invest in their professional growth.

Sexism and gender harassment

N.	Measures/actions	Objective
10	Strengthen the existing system for combat against sexual harassment and discrimination	FER will continue to implement, monitor and improve the existing system with the aim of strengthening the trust in the institution and providing a safe and dignified environment to all its students, staff and guests. FER will continue to ensure equal access to information for all employees and students.

Collaborative actions

N.	Area	Measures/actions	Objective
1	Human resources	Pilot program for empowerment of female researchers	The implementation of this measure will provide specific professional development for young researchers and will increase awareness of the removal of barriers to the inclusion of women in research and innovation. The long-term goal of this measure is to remove barriers to the appointment of women to management positions and scientific positions and to reduce the impact of the leaky pipeline phenomenon, which describes how women are becoming an under-represented minority in STEM areas. The lecturers and mentors will be women who occupy leading positions in organizations from the innovation ecosystem of FER.
2	Teaching	Integration of the gender dimension in teaching	The measure envisages the gathering of a group of teachers with the aim of exploring the integration of the gender dimension in the curriculum. Exploring

			contemporary approaches to teaching will strengthen institutional capacity in teaching and raise teachers' awareness of gender equality. In the long run, this measure will raise the institutional capacity to integrate the gender dimension into research and innovation and will strengthen innovation in research. It is planned to include teachers from other higher education institutions in the work of the group.
3	Transfer to market	Promotion of the principles of gender equality in technology transfer	The measure envisages promotional activities aimed at the female researchers involved in technology transfer and the promotion of gender equality towards external stakeholders. In the long run, the implementation of this measure will contribute to the further integration of the principles of gender equality in all aspects of cooperation with stakeholders from the innovation ecosystem and to the increase in the number of projects that integrate the gender dimension. A FemTech event will be organized, and stakeholders from the innovation ecosystem of FER will participate in panels, workshops and promotional activities of the event.
4	Students service	Attracting new students	The aim of this measure is to attract new female students and raise awareness of stereotypes about technical occupations as exclusively male. One of the main events will be FemTech during which female role models from the innovation ecosystem of FER will present their career path and offer encouragement to perspective students.

8 YASAR's GEP

The GEP elaborated by the Yaşar University (Turkey) represents a first version which will undergo two implementation phases and a re-design/adjustment step between the two.

The English version of the GEP has already been presented to the Rector as on the 30th of June 2021. After the translation of the document, it will be submitted to the signature of the Rectorate and afterwards to the approval of the Board of Trustees. The latest English version of the GEP is available at the following [link](#).

The document includes 17 measures tackling six main areas: human resources, institutional governance, research, teaching, institutional communication, sexual harassment.

Figure 10: YASAR's GEP Key Priority Areas

The strategic areas and proposed measures have been carefully chosen and discussed with the top and middle management.

The Gender Equality Strategy of the YU aims to improve gender equality in human resources area by updating recruitment and promotion procedures and establishing measures to support career progression of the underrepresented gender at the institutional level. In order to achieve and maintain gender equality in all priority areas it is also important to monitor the processes by collecting gender-disaggregated data.

To ensure gender equality in institutional governance, YU will finalize the establishment of the gender equality body (Women Studies Research Center-YUKAM) as responsible unit for gender research and teaching and project development purposes (which can be considered transversal to the research area) and organize activities to increase the awareness of the top-level management regarding gender balance in decision making processes. YU will also develop and implement an empowerment programme to support young female researchers. Furthermore, an official 'declaration of will' which is aimed to demonstrate YU's commitment to gender equality in decision making will be prepared.

In the area of research, measures to integrate gender into institutional strategic plan and institutional funding mechanisms and awareness raising activities on the application of gender analysis and gender dimension into research will be implemented. Additionally, a Gender Researchers Group will be established.

In order to ensure gender-sensitive teaching practices guidelines on the integration of the gender dimension into curricula and teaching will be prepared and pilot training and implementation will be carried out in one department from each faculty.

The measures of development and implementation of gender-sensitive institutional communication guidelines and training of relevant staff members on gender-sensitive institutional communication are aimed at incorporating gender equality as a core value and a part of institutional identity through promoting gender-sensitive communication.

Finally, Gender Equality Strategy of the YU includes measures to show its commitment to prevention of gender-based discrimination, violence and sexual harassment. To this end, an institutional policy document will be prepared and a unit will be established to prevent gender-based discrimination, violence and sexual harassment.

As far as the collaborative actions are concerned, 3 actions are included in the GEP tackling the areas of research, sexual harassment, institutional communication, teaching and students services (actions tackle more than one area). They involve all type of organizations (e.g. universities, public organizations, NGOs, business sector, schools).

Here below all the actions included in the YASAR's GEP in its version as at the 30th June 2021 are listed.

Human Resources

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
1	Gender-sensitive recruitment procedures	Integrate gender equality into the recruitment process	Jan 2022 – Jun 2022
2	Revision of the promotion criteria of staff	Set up transparent and flexible criteria for the promotion of staff	Jan 2022 – Jun 2022
3	Support measures for underrepresented gender at the institutional level	Establish measures to support career progression of the underrepresented gender at the institutional level	Jan 2022 – Jun 2022

Institutional governance

N.	Measures/actions	Objective
4	Gender equality body	Establish a gender equality body
5	Gender-disaggregated data collection	Establish gender-disaggregated data collection procedures
6	Awareness-raising activities	Increase awareness of the top-level management regarding gender balance in decision making processes
7	Empowerment programme	Develop and implement an empowerment programme to support young female researchers
8	Declaration of will for gender equality in decision making	Prepare and implement principles/plan for providing gender equality in decision making bodies.

Research

N.	Measures/actions	Objective (short-term)
9	Integration of gender into institutional strategic plan and institutional funding mechanisms	Integrate of gender subjects into the institutional strategic plan and institutional funding mechanisms
10	Awareness raising actions	Organization of awareness raising activities (workshops, training) on the application of gender analysis and gender dimension into research
11	Gender Researchers Group	Establish a Gender Researchers Group at the university.

Teaching

N.	Measures/actions	Objective
12	Guidelines on the integration of the gender dimension into curricula and teaching	Development and adoption of principles for integrating the gender dimension into curricula and teaching
13	Training and pilot implementation	Training of academic staff on gender-sensitive teaching and pilot implementation of the curriculum with a gender dimension in one department from each faculty.

Communication

N.	Measures/actions	Objective
14	Gender-sensitive institutional communication guidelines	Development and implementation of gender-sensitive institutional communication guidelines
15	Gender-sensitive communication trainings	Training of relevant staff members gender-sensitive institutional communication

Sexual harassment

N.	Measures/actions	Objective
16	Creation of an institutional policy document	Development and adoption of a policy document against sexism and sexual harassment
17	Gender Based Discrimination, Violence and Sexual Harassment Prevention Unit	Establishment of Gender Based Discrimination, Violence and Sexual Harassment Prevention Unit

Collaborative actions

n.	Collaborative action	Area	Stakeholders involved	Timeframe
1	Collaborative research and projects	Research	Universities, public organizations, municipalities	Sept 2021-August 2023
2	Awareness raising and capacity building trainings	Sexual harassment, Institutional communication	NGOs, professional organizations, universities, public organizations	Jan 2022- August 2023
3	The FemTech Events	Teaching Student Services	Universities, business sector, professional organizations, public organizations, schools	Sept 2021– August 2023

9 MTF STU's GEP

The GEP elaborated by the Faculty of Materials Science and Technology, as one of the faculties of the Slovak University of Technology, has been submitted to the Dean and as at the 30th of June 2021 has not been approved yet. It will undergo the approval process firstly by the Faculty management and later by the Academic Senate of the Faculty, in order to be integrated into the Faculty Strategy.

The current version of the GEP is available at the following [link](#).

The GEP counts of 13 actions tackling 6 main areas: institutional governance, human resources, communication, research, teaching, transfer to market and sexual harassment.

Figure 11: MTF STU's GEP Key Priority Areas

The most strategic area has been identified in the one of institutional governance, where 4 actions have been included. The aim is to change the faculty's vision and mission and to create a balanced internal culture through the adoption of an Extra Action Plan and of a Gender & Diversity Monitory system.

As far as the human resources area is concerned, the "recruitment" and "career breaks and job reintegration" sub-areas have been addressed with the creation of protocols and programs, while within communication the focus is on awareness raising activities.

Concerning research and teaching, the GEP includes measures aimed at integrating the gender dimension in research projects, thesis and courses curricula.

In the area of transfer to market, the action concerns the increase of the number of female academics involved in collaborative projects with companies and the number of females obtaining patents.

Finally, within the area of sexual harassment, the main action consists in the establishment of a "complaints system".

As far as collaborative actions are concerned, 3 actions are included in the plan and are related to the communication area. They involve stakeholders of the academia, public sector, schools and business sector.

Here below all the actions included in the version as at the 30th of June 2021 of the MTF STU's GEP are listed.

Human Resources

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
1	Creation of gender-sensitive protocols for recruitment and hiring.	Guarantee equal conditions during hiring process.	September 2021 – December 2022
2	Creation of programs for employees' reintegration and development	Simplify the comeback from the break in science, support of the academic growth.	September 2021 – June 2023

Institutional governance

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
3	Development of an Extra Action Plan	Official document entitled Extra Action Plan at MTF STU with one part dedicated to equal opportunities with emphasis on gender equality.	June 2021- December 2021
4	Delegates	Creation of a network of delegates who will work on the area of gender equality activities at the faculty.	September 2021 – August 2023
5	Methodological handbooks	At least 3 methodological handbooks intended for the internal public (employees and students) of MTF STU.	January 2022 – August 2023
6	Gender & Diversity Controlling	Establishment of a monitoring system to control all GEP activities.	January 2022 – August 2023

Research

N.	Measures/actions	Objective (short-term)	Timeframe of implementation
7	Integration of the gender dimension in final theses (bachelor's degrees, diploma, dissertations)	Increasing awareness of gender equality by raising the number of theses (bachelor's degrees, diploma, dissertations) with the gender equality topic.	September 2021 – August 2023
8	Integration of gender issues and the gender dimension into research projects (as well as scientific publications).	Information, dissemination of knowledge, researched information among the scientific, professional and public fields through the integration of gender issues into research projects.	September 2021 – August 2023

Teaching

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
9	Integration of gender in the curriculum.	Within the existing syllabi and curricula of selected subjects to include one lecture on the issue of gender equality and to include some selected topics / lectures in the curriculum.	September 2021 – August 2023

Communication

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
10	Online and offline activities, workshops, games	By the females of MTF STU promotion: - Raise the number of women at the academic level and among students - Raise the awareness of the gender equality topic	September 2021 – August 2023

Transfer to market

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
11	Support to all academics (especially women) in technology transfer	Increasing the number of academics (with special emphasis on increasing the number of women) involved in Transfer to market by obtaining patents. Maintaining the current state of cooperation with enterprises.	September 2021 – August 2023

Sexual harassment

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
12	Creation of an institutional policy document	Development and adoption of a policy document against sexism and sexual harassment	July 2021 – August 2023
13	Gender Based Discrimination, Violence and Sexual Harassment Prevention Unit	Establishment of Gender Based Discrimination, Violence and Sexual Harassment Prevention Unit	September 2021 – August 2023

Collaborative actions

n.	Collaborative action	Area	Stakeholders involved	Timeframe
1	Communication strategy	Communication	Industrial enterprises, municipalities	June 2021 – August 2023
2	Open days, information panels, lectures	Communication	Schools and universities	June 2021 – August 2023
3	Raising awareness on the importance of equal chances and opportunities	Communication	Municipalities, businesses, schools, universities	July 2021 - August 2023

10 ECE NTUA's GEP

The School of Electrical and Computer Engineering of the National Technical University of Athens in Greece (ECE-NTUA) has elaborated the current version of the GEP, available at this [link](#), which has received the endorsement by the Deanery, while the approval by the General Assembly is expected within July 2021.

The GEP includes actions in all the areas: human resources, institutional governance, communication, research, teaching, students' services, transfer to market, sexual harassment, and intersectionality.

Overall, 12 actions have been included in the plan.

Figure 12: NTUA's GEP Key Priority Areas

As regards the human resources area the main goals of the adopted measures are to gradually increase the number of women at all levels of the School (undergraduate, postgraduate, PhD candidates, researchers) and create an inclusive environment and improve the working conditions through the elimination of insecurities and discouragement of potential sexist behaviour. As concerns the Institutional Governance area, it includes more structural actions such as the set up of a Gender Equality Office and the establishment of system for collecting gender disaggregated data. The communication area instead is addressed through the application of guidelines for non-sexist language and awareness raising activities. Referring to research the Gender Equality strategy aims to integrate the gender dimension into research projects, scientific publications and raise the number of female Principal Investigators, while within the Teaching and Students services areas, actions for the integration of the gender dimension into teaching through the implementation of lectures and the elaboration of compulsory seminars are included. As regards the Transfer to Market area, the creation of an Alumni Network is foreseen in order to establish more adequate transfer to market activities. Within the sexual harassment and gender violence area the target of the plan includes the establishment of an appropriate mechanism to frame, prevent and handle gender violence/sexual harassment issues. Finally, about intersectionality, a system of collecting and analysing intersectional data will be set up in order to introduce the topic in the School.

As far as collaborative actions are concerned, 5 are included in the plan, tackling the areas of communication, research and students services and involving 10 stakeholders belonging to the academia and the civil society sectors.

Here below all the actions included in the version as at the 30th of June 2021 of the NTUA's GEP are listed.

Human Resources

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
1	Internal targets (gender indicators) regarding the desired % of female representation among students, researchers, academics and female representation in recruiting boards (Electing Committees)	Assist decision making and set internal goals to have a clear vision of desired improvements.	Oct 2021 – Aug 2023
2	Formal, structured mechanism to handle incidents of bias and sexist behaviour in the working environment	Encourage appropriate conduct while raising awareness and offer adequate training of how to handle incidents.	Nov 2021 – Aug 2023
3	Guide framing research and post – doc education conditions in the School (in order to create a more stable environment for researchers)	Eliminate insecurities and establish a more stable working environment.	Dec 21 – Aug 2023

Institutional governance

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
4	Gender Equality Office	Support, lead, coordinate and embed gender equality and diversity actions at School level, while cooperating with the established NTUA Gender Equality Committee.	Oct 2021 – Aug 2023
5	Collection of gender disaggregated data	Collection of gender disaggregated data for the provision of information and design of suitable actions.	Apr 2022 – Aug 2023

Research

N.	Measures/actions	Objective (short-term)	Timeframe of implementation
6	Internal target and indicator “Number of thesis/PhD’s/research projects with a gender dimension in their content” (as part of the School’s performance assessment)	Create a framework for measuring the inclusion of gender in research content, and initiate discussions on how to improve performance.	Oct 2021 – Aug 2023

Teaching

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
7	Integration of gender-related topics in selected courses and lectures	Directly include gender-related topics in courses/lectures where it is appropriate to do so	Oct 2021 – Aug 2023

Communication

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
8	Support the application of the “Guide of using non-sexist language in administrative documents”	- Ensure that official communications use gender-balanced and use gender sensitive language	Nov 2021 – Aug 2023

Students services

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
9	Seminar on gender topics for students	Improve awareness of gender topics and appropriate behaviour among students	Jul 2022 – Aug 2023

Transfer to market

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
10	Creation of an Alumni Network	The creation of an alumni network , which will include a focus on gender and working in combination with the collaborative networking activities will enhance the communication between the market and the School support towards new graduates in order to establish more adequate transfer to the market.	Oct 2022 – Aug 2023

Sexual harassment

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
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11	Formal mechanism dealing with cases of sexual harassment and gender violence	Improve the reporting and resolution of harassment incidents, raise awareness regarding appropriate conduct	Nov 2021 – Aug 2023
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Intersectionality

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
12	Collection of Gender Equality data on Intersectionality	Provision of better understanding of how members of the School perceive gender equality and implement respective actions, when necessary.	Apr 2022 – Aug 2023

Collaborative actions

n.	Collaborative action	Area	Stakeholders involved	Timeframe
1	Engagement of Role models and dissemination activities	Human Resources, Institutional Governance	Professional & Research Communities (2), Universities (1: NTUA ⁶ Liaison Office), Industry, Scientific Associations (1)	Sep 2021 – Aug 2023
2	Creation of a “Women in STEM” Network	Human Resources, Research, Transfer to market	Professional & Research Communities (1), Universities (1: NTUA Liaison Office), Industry, Scientific Associations, CSOs (Civil Society Organizations) (1), Research Centers	Oct 2022 – Aug 2023
3	ECE-NTUA Open days	Human Resources, Institutional Governance	Schools, NGO’s, Professional & Research Communities, Scientific Associations, Universities (1+1: NTUA Liaison Office)	Mar 2022 – Aug 2023
4	Information Days and Training Workshops on gender issues in STEM	Institutional Communication, Research, Teaching, Sexual Harassment, Intersectionality	Professional & Research Communities (2), Universities (2+1: NTUA Liaison Office), Industry (1), Scientific Associations (1), CSO’s (1)	Nov 2021 – Aug 2023
5	FEM – TECH Events	Transfer to Market	Professional & Research	Sep 2021 – Nov 2021

⁶ Note that the NTUA Liaison Office operates at the level of the National Technical University of Athens, and is independent of the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering

			Communities (2), Universities (1: NTUA Liaison Office), Industry (1), Scientific Associations, NGO's, Research Centers	
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11 UEFISCDI's GEP

UEFISCDI positions itself as the first Romanian public institution (RFO) elaborating and implementing a Gender Equality Plan. The goal of its gender equality strategy is to help UEFISCDI brand itself as a leading actor in the innovation ecosystem and at the same time as a good practice in gender equality for both other Romanian public institutions and other research entities (RPOs).

The document has not been approved yet by the top management as at the 30th of June 2021. The current version is available at the present [link](#).

The GEP tackles 6 areas: human resources, institutional governance, communication, research funding, transfer to market and sexual harassment, with 11 measures.

Figure 13: UEFISCDI's GEP Key Priority Areas

Actions within the human resources area are aimed at raising the awareness of recruiters about gender stereotypes as well as at supporting employees in the process of returning from parental leaves by also improving their skills (e.g. through a mentoring programme) and their work-life balance. The Institutional governance area is addressed by the establishment of a Gender Equality Body, to be in charge of the implementation and supervision of the GEP. The adoption of guidelines on gender sensitive communication/language is instead the purpose of the action included in the communication area. With reference to the most peculiar activity of UEFISCDI, research funding, the actions included in the plan are aimed at conducting a study to understand the reasons why women participate less in research programs with respect to men and how they could be encouraged, and at training research evaluators on gender equality, also through the elaboration of an informative kit. A kit is also foreseen in the sexual harassment area to raise the awareness on the issue within the institution's employees. Finally, as far as the transfer to market area is concerned, the action included concerns the implementation of quotas/targets within events/conferences when inviting speakers.

2 collaborative actions have been included in the plan. They target different areas, especially human resources and involve stakeholders from academia and the business sector.

Here below all the actions included in the version as at the 30th of June 2021 of the UEFISCDI's GEP are listed.

Human Resources

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
1	Informative kit with specific instructions regarding gender discrimination and stereotypes identification in the recruiting process	To help the recruitment experts to become aware of the stereotypes that they might unconsciously experience in the recruiting process.	July 2021 – Dec 2021
2	Back to work training	To help employees returning from parental leave to get accustomed to the recent developments in the institution and the projects they were working on previously	Sept 2021- June 2022
3	Soft skills training	to increase work efficiency and improve work life balance for employees returning from parental leave	Sept 2021- Apr 2022
4	Mentoring for leadership positions	To increase the number of employees fit for leadership positions	Sept 2021 - June2022
5	Internal educational program	On one hand, to help employees acknowledge their latent potential, and on the other hand to provide to middle managers, information about other abilities and interests of their employees	Sept 2021 - June2022

Institutional governance

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
6	Establishing of the GEB	To establish a body in charge of the implementation and supervision of the GEP, ensuring that its composition is balanced and effective for a successful implementation of GEP	July 2021 – Dec 2021

Research funding

N.	Measures/actions	Objective (short-term)	Timeframe of implementation
7	Analysis of women participation in research projects	- To understand the reasons why women participate in smaller numbers in research	Sept 2021 – June 2022

		<p>programs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -to understand how the content of research is affected - to identify ways in which women researchers can be encouraged to join research areas dominated mainly by men 	
8	Training for research evaluators regarding the gender dimension	-to assure that when evaluating projects with gender components evaluators are able to recognize them and they do not misinterpret because of ideological beliefs	Sept 2021 – June 2022

Communication

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
9	Informative gender sensitive communication kit	To assure that all institutional communication , both internal and external, is gender sensitive	July 2021 – Dec 2021

Transfer to market

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
10	Implementing quotas/targets when inviting speakers at the events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to have a better representation of women at the event - to better address gender sensitive topics 	July 2021 – Dec 2021

Sexual harassment

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
11	Informative kit regarding sexual and moral harassment	Raising awareness about sexual and moral harassment and help identification of harassments' types and clearly explain the concept (definition, limits, etc)	July 2021 – Dec 2021

Collaborative actions

n.	Collaborative action	Area	Stakeholders involved	Timeframe
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1	Development of informative kits	Human resources, Sexual Harassment, Research Funding, Internal & External Communication	Centru FILIA, University of Bucharest	July 2021 – Dec 2021
2	Trainings on career progression	Human resources	Orange Fab Lab, Step FWD, TechHub Bucharest	Sept 2021 – June 2022

12 SRNSFG's GEP

The Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (RFO) developed its first GEP, which was then presented and submitted to the top management for the approval. The GEP was signed and approved by the General Director of the Foundation on the 30th of June 2021. The final version of the document is available at the present [link](#).

SRNSFG has adopted the gender equality strategy targeting the main challenges identified during the internal and external assessment. SRNSFG aims to support the involvement of more female researchers in STEM, improving their careers prospects and integrating a gender dimension into research.

Key areas of the strategy are: research funding, human resources and institutional communication. However, the strategy also targets other areas according to the emerged challenges: institutional governance, sexual harassment and intersectionality.

Figure 14: SRNSFG's GEP Key Priority Areas

Overall, 15 actions have been included in the GEP. Actions within the human resources area tackle existing gender issues through trainings and raising awareness activities, as well as the work-life balance of employees through dedicated measures. As concerns institutional governance, actions mainly aim at setting up a gender disaggregated data collection system, while an ad hoc strategy for gender sensitive communication has been included in the related area. With reference to the most peculiar area of research funding, actions include the introduction of a gender balance control mechanism in scientific teams and the elaboration of specific guidelines and training on gender stereotypes and bias for evaluators and committee members. The adoption of a sexual harassment policy and of a mechanism for reporting cases are instead foreseen as actions within the sexual harassment area. Finally, as regards intersectionality, the plan includes the set up of a system for collecting disaggregated data by gender in conjunction with ethnicity, gender identity, age, disability and other dimensions.

For what concerns collaborative actions, 7 have been included and they are related to the areas of research and communication and involve mainly stakeholders belonging to the academia sector.

Here below all the actions included in the version as at the 30th of June 2021 of the SRNSFG's GEP are listed.

Human Resources

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
1	Training for the staff involved in recruitment process	Raising awareness about gender equality issues and ensuring that every person involved in the recruitment process is aware of gender-issues, discrimination and stereotypes	October 2021 - March 2022
2	Informational brochure/guide to recruited staff about gender equality	Raising awareness about gender equality and ensuring that every person who starts working at Foundation is aware of gender-issues.	November 2021
3	Development of exit questionnaire for staff	Understand the reasons why employees leave the organization from a gender perspective.	December 2021
4	Training and other activities improving professional skills of staff	Improve professional skills of the Foundation staff and contribute to their career development.	October 2021 - December 2022

Institutional governance

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
5	Collecting gender disaggregated data at the organization institutional level	To set gender disaggregated data and update it regularly, with the aim of monitoring gender balance at organization level;	October, 2021
6	Modifying existing job descriptions in the administration unit of SRNSFG, by adding targeted functions towards gender related issues in the organization	To add targeted functions to Promote and monitor gender related issues in the organization and ensure supporting gender balance at staff and higher management levels;	September, 2021

Research funding

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
7	Research about the gender balance in research teams at the project registration stage	Ensuring gender balance and eliminating discrimination in research teams	December, 2021 – June, 2022
8	Establishing reward for woman scientists	Establishing an award for women scientists working in various scientific fields. Encouraging their activities and introducing successful women scientist to the wider community in Georgia	January, 2022 – June, 2022

9	Providing evaluators/committee members gender related guidelines	Providing evaluators/committee members with specific guidelines on gender stereotypes, unconscious bias and training will ensure successful evaluation process without any kind of gender bias.	September, 2021 – March, 2022
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Communication

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
10	Strategy encompassing measures/actions related to the institutional communication enhancement on the matter of gender equality: conferences, webinars, workshops, symposia, special training.	To encourage SRNSFG institutional capacities by creating special policy envisaging concrete measures and focusing on awareness raising	September, 2021 – June, 2022
11	Special section on the website revealing successful Georgian women in STEM/research.	One of the “example giving” steps from the side of SRNSFG to demonstrate the will for women enhancement and at the same time to get popular Georgian female researchers.	September, 2021- December, 2021
12	Strategic communication plan based on all aspects that could motivate all internal/external stakeholders to become active participants in developing institutional communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To support the harmonization of STEM system; To establish a sustainable and efficient ground for Georgian STEM eco-system. 	September, 2021 – June, 2022

Sexual harassment

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
13	Sexual Harassment Policy.	Adopt a formal policy that forbids sexual harassment.	January, 2022 - March, 2022
14	Mechanism for reporting.	Make sexual harassment policy effective.	January, 2022 - March, 2022

Intersectionality

N.	Measures/actions	Objective	Timeframe of implementation
15	Gender disaggregated data collection system taking into account other dimensions such as ethnicity, gender identity, age, disability, religion, etc.	Ensure that data collection does not overlook the experiences of individuals with intersectional identities and ensure an inclusive and transparent system of data collection.	December, 2021- June, 2022

Collaborative actions

n.	Collaborative action	Area	Stakeholders involved	Timeframe
1	ToR for Annual Female Scientists Award with academia and universities	Research	Academia and Universities	January, 2022 – June, 2022
2	Guidelines for the integration of the gender dimension for evaluators/committee members	Research	Academia and Universities	September, 2021 – March, 2022
3	Collaboration in the process of creating gender dimension in the evaluation criteria for the future grant calls	Research	Academia and Universities	December, 2021 – June, 2022
4	Femtech event	Research	Academia and Universities, Public Sector	April, 2022
5	Special targeted events, conference, symposia (e.g., in the frame of “Science Fest” one conference dedicated for Georgian Female Researchers)	Communication	Academia and Universities	September, 2021- October, 2021
6	Exchange of information about women researchers with stakeholders for dissemination purposes	Communication	Academia and Universities	September, 2021- June, 2022
7	Raising awareness activities to motivate all internal/external stakeholders to become active participants in developing institutional communication	Communication	Academia and Universities	September, 2021- June, 2022

Concluding remarks

From the analysis of the GEPs presented in the previous chapters, it emerges how the great majority of the documents have started their approval process and have been submitted to the authorities and/or decision-making bodies in charge. The only exception is represented by the SRNSFG's GEP which has been already signed and approved by the General Director of the Foundation. All the other GEPs will undergo a multiple step process for the final approval, which will take place between July and November 2021.

As already specified in the previous chapters, GEPs might be subject to amendments and integration within the approval process, therefore, the actions listed in each GEPs' chapter might not fully correspond to the ones included in the final versions of the documents.

The analysis provided in chapter 3 shows that institutional change processes have already started to take place in several of the partner institutions as change dynamics were already in place and have been further triggered by the CALIPER project (see IRB, ULB, YASAR and UNISALENTO, for example). Overall the GEPs and the processes and the broad inclusive dialogues which have accompanied their design and approval, show that a change process is triggered and sustained in all RPOs and RFOs: in fact, all the areas/topics have been tackled by CALIPER's partners, with GEPs addressing from 6 to 9 areas each. All partners have included actions in the areas of human resources, institutional governance, research/research funding and communication. All in all, we acknowledge a good level of uptake and localization of the supporting measures and models that have been provided between WP1 and WP2. Yet, the emerging picture is extremely varied and depends on the national and institutional contexts and circumstances, with some partners moving in a more straightforward way by introducing structural actions already in this initial version of the GEP such as creation of GE bodies, or setting up new recruitment protocols, or creating reporting mechanisms on sexual harassment, for example. Others have initiated a more gradual path with most softer measures included in the GEPs and aimed at raising awareness, further capacity building or more exploratory measures. As far as collaborative actions are concerned, all areas have been addressed, except the ones of institutional governance and intersectionality. The high number of collaborative actions included (42) and of the involved external stakeholders (176) represents a very promising outcome of the actions undertaken by partners for the involvement of the innovation ecosystems and in particular of the dialogues with the R&I Hubs conducted in the frame of T2.2 and T2.3.

The actions included in the GEPs will be implemented starting from M19 (July 2021) and will undergo two implementation iterations, with a re-design phase in between. Within the implementation phase, the formative evaluation will take place with the aim of getting feedback on the actions while they are being implemented, ensuring their progress complies with the planning, as well as feeding the re-design phase.

Annex I: T2.3 Guidelines

CALIPER
Gender Equality in STEM Research

Linking Research & Innovation for
Gender Equality

T2.3_Guidelines

Version n. 2

23/04/2021

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1 Introduction

The present document is the second version of the guidelines elaborated within Task 2.3 about “GEPs design and development”, which include further inputs with reference, in particular, to sections 3 and 5 compared with the first version released on the 2nd April 2021.

The guidelines are meant to serve as an useful tool to support partners in the GEP design process together with the repository of resources elaborated by Smart Venice and available in [Team Work](#), which provides plenty of good-practices to get inspiration from.

In the frame of Task 2.3, each partner’s Working Group will set up an internal consultation with middle and top management representatives in order to identify the most appropriate **strategy** and a set of **feasible solutions** to address the existing challenges previously identified in Task 2.1, and to be included in the GEP. The strategy and feasible solutions will then be exposed to feedback from the **Research and Innovation Hubs** through an additional workshop. The process will then lead to the finalization of the first version of the GEP by the CALIPER WGs and teams, to be submitted to the top management for the approval.

In order to facilitate the discussion with the middle and top management, partners are recommended to share the infographic summarizing the results of the internal and external assessment (the so called “mini report”) as well as to elaborate **concept maps** which would show the findings of the scenarios elaborated in task 2.1 and of the results of the dialogues with the R&I Hubs of task 2.2. The following section will provide useful tips about how to prepare concept maps. Section 3 focuses on co-creation meetings with high and middle management, section 4 on the 2nd R&I dialogues, section 5 on final GEPs’ design, to conclude with a summary of the Task’s deadlines in section 6.

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2 How to prepare a concept map

A concept map is a visual representation of information and ideas. It represents **relationships between concepts or ideas** and helps in organising and structuring the information¹. A concept map is structured with nodes and labelled arrows. General concepts occupy high positions in the structure and concepts that have the same element are grouped on the same branch. A concept map can be useful, among others, for representing information about connections and for brainstorming, which is the use that will be done within task 2.3.

A concept map can be simply drawn by hand or by using a software program. Examples of programs that allow to create simple concept maps are Lucid² and Miro³. They are also collaborative tools that permit working simultaneously on the same map. Therefore, in the frame of the consultation meetings, that most likely will happen online, they can be used as shared tools for facilitating the discussion and possibly working in groups⁴.

It is suggested to elaborate a concept map for **each thematic area** (e.g. human resources, institutional governance, teaching, research, etc.) and within each thematic area prepare additional maps per each sub-area if need be, in case the map risks to become too congested.

Here below we briefly describe the different steps to follow in the creation of a concept map. Consider that it is a visual representation, therefore information should be summarized as much as possible. It is also suggested to use different colors for each kind of node.

Step 1

Go through the three scenarios you have elaborated in task 2.1 and for each area (and eventually sub-area) identify the main problems that emerged and report them in the map, also indicating briefly the causes connected with the problems.

Step 2

Under each problem, report the solutions (if you have indicated many, report the main ones or the ones that you consider more feasible) that you have identified and add the main resistances that you have reported related to the solutions (in the image n.1 below, resistances are indicated with a post-it).

Step 3

Go through the report of the first dialogue with the R&I Hub and identify the common challenges that emerged with reference to the specific area (or sub-area) and highlight them in the map (in figure n.1 the common challenges are highlighted with a red star).

¹ <http://explainwell.org/index.php/table-of-contents-map-your-knowledge/what-is-a-concept-map/>

² <https://lucid.co/product/lucidchart> first 3 maps are free.

³ <https://miro.com/templates/concept-map/>

⁴ Another collaborative tool that can be used for online workshops is Mural <https://www.mural.co/>

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Step 4

Focus on the possible collaborative/joint actions that emerged during the dialogues with stakeholders and report them in the map, making them visible also using different colors, as well as connecting them with the common challenges and with the solutions which were (eventually) identified in the scenarios.

The exercise will result with a map similar to the one represented in the figure below. Please consider that the picture is only an example of structure for the conceptual map, the content is made up for explanatory purposes only.

Figure n. 1: Example of concept map related to the area of institutional governance⁵

⁵ In the picture, the red stars identify the common challenges with external stakeholders while the post-it the resistances related to the identified solution.

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The map can be complemented with additional information and adapted in the way that is considered most appropriate. As already mentioned, it should serve as a basis to facilitate brainstorming with middle and top management. Moreover, by using collaboration tools (e.g. Lucid, Miro, Mural) it will be possible to work on the maps in a collaborative way.

The maps can be elaborated in the local language and do not need to be translated and uploaded in teamwork since they are considered internal working documents.

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3 Organizing an internal consultation with middle and top management

The GEPs design process will start with the organization by each partner's WG of a further internal consultation with middle and top management. The consultation is aimed at presenting to the management the results of the previous steps through the elaborated tools ("mini reports" and concept maps) as well as discussing and finalizing the Gender Equality strategy of the institution: the strategy articulates a set of feasible solutions/actions to put in place (and include in the GEP) in order to address the previously identified challenges. The GE strategy sets priorities, identifies key internal stakeholders in charge of solutions/actions, as well as opportunities to leverage upon. It doesn't go deep into detailing each action.

The internal consultation with middle and top management should involve managers covering roles in all the relevant areas which will be involved in the GEP, and has the goal of defining each GEP action in detail. The process we suggest to follow for the implementation of the internal consultation is the following and presented as a linear one: it still might be that more back-and-forth meetings will be needed.

- A. Set up an initial meeting between the WG and the **top management** (e.g. Rector, Vice-rector, Directors, Deans, etc.) for identifying overall priorities and a strategy. Indicative deadline: mid April.
- B. Once the overall priorities and a strategy are identified, parallel meetings with **middle management** and all those internal actors/actresses involved in the GEP design as well as in the actions will be organized. It is suggested to organize a meeting for each area that is going to be addressed in the GEP, or eventually combine areas in case all the relevant internal actors/actresses are present. **The purpose of the meetings is to identify and analyse a set of feasible solutions/actions per each area, therefore the identification of the persons to involve in the meetings is crucial at this stage**, since they will be the ones to be directly implicated in the implementation of the identified actions/measures. The analysis of the identified actions will be conducted using the template shown in paragraph 3.1. Deadline: end of April/first week of May.
- C. Meeting with the WG to **finalize the GEP**. Deadline: end of May/beginning of June.
- D. Presentation of the GEP and its approval by the relevant institutional body. Deadline: end of June.

The initial meeting with the WG and the top management (point A), as already mentioned, is aimed at identifying the overall strategies and priorities of the organization according to the results of the previous activities carried out. As mentioned, the WG will indeed make use of the infographics including the results of the internal and external assessments (the so called "mini report") as well as of the concept maps elaborated according to section n. 2 of the present document, as a basis for the discussion. In order to ensure a co-design/collaborative approach, it is recommended to use **collaboration tools** such as Lucid, Miro and Mural (links indicated above), which permit to work simultaneously, visualize the concept maps and gather inputs from all the participants of the meeting. The outcome of the meeting should flow into a report that can be elaborated using the template available as Annex A.

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3.1 Designing the identified actions

3.1.1 Introducing the design steps and tools

As already mentioned, the meetings with middle management foreseen at point B of the previous paragraph are meant to identify and define/design feasible solutions/actions to be included in the GEP. In order to integrate design with evaluation and monitoring of the implementation since the early stages of GEPs design, the design of actions and measures to be included in the GEPs will make use of the “log-frame” (see figure figure n. 2) elaborated by FUOC within the in-progress work under WP4. We recommend to use it already for the discussion and the analysis of the different solutions/actions with the middle management. This is in order to ensure a collaborative approach and the co-design of the actions. If suitable, the tool can be shared and filled in by using one of the online collaboration tools already mentioned above, to ensure the interactivity of the process⁶.

It is important to point out that a log-frame template needs to be elaborated per each single action/measure that will be included in the GEP, even for those actions/measures that will be implemented collaboratively with stakeholders of the R&I Hubs.

In order to fill the log-frames in, partners can directly re-work the image included in Figure 2 making it editable by using dedicated graphic design softwares, or alternatively use the table available as Annex C.

After the consultation with the middle management, the WG will finalize the log-frames and send them to Smart Venice by the end of May 2021, together with an overall report of the meetings with the middle management using the template available as Annex B. The log-frame templates need, therefore, to be also prepared in English and they will be included in D2.3. Indeed, they will serve as starting points for the elaboration of the GEP (see section 5) and at the same time represent the core part of the Plans themselves.

⁶ More concretely, it is suggested to copy and paste the log-frame in a collaboration tool (the most suitable for this purpose is in our opinion Miro) and allow all participants of the meeting to enter it and contribute by using “sticky notes”. Alternatively, you can reproduce the content of the tool in a Word file (or Google doc) using Annex C, and share it with the participants.

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Figure n. 2: Log-frame for the design analysis coming from the CALIPER evaluation methodology

In what follows, we will provide a detailed description of the log-frame and its elements, according to the WP4 methodology which is currently in progress.

3.1.2 Using the log-frame to design GEPs actions

Designing an intervention/action requires to gather all the needed information in order to be able to answers to the following questions:

- **Who is the audience of the intervention, who is addressed?** For example, PhD candidates or school teachers?
- **What are the goals of an intervention?** For example, to attract more girls to STEM careers.
- **What are the expected outcomes and impact?** For example, to provide less stereotypical career choices.
- **Which activities are planned?** For example, an awareness raising campaign.
- **What are suitable indicators to monitor progress?** For example, more female students in STEM degree courses.
- **Which resources are available to implement the intervention?** Part-time position; collaboration with NGO.

The above-mentioned elements are brought together by the so-called “log-frame”. A log-frame is an instrument to build an overarching story about how a specific GEP intervention is supposed to work.

In addition to the analysis of the target audience, the goals and activities, a log-frame incorporates an analysis of the facilitating and hindering contextual factors of an intervention. National or regional policy frameworks are such contextual factors together with the organizational working environment.

A log-frame furthermore provides an instrument to create an awareness of the complexity involved for initiating and

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sustaining organizational change processes. Good log-frames consult the existing scientific literature to provide evidence on the likelihood of certain interventions to be successful.

The log-frame template introduces the **main building blocks for the design of an intervention**.

The example used for explanation purpose in this paragraph is a specifically adapted version of a **mentoring program for early career researchers** taken from the Efforti Impact Story Knowledge Base⁷.

EXAMPLE

As women are underrepresented in research and leadership positions within academia, the purpose of mentoring programs are to contribute to improving the female talent pool for career progression by strengthening women mentees' professional and/or leadership skills and career prospects through planning, prioritising, networking and insights into organisational norms, processes and policies.

Mentoring schemes may take different forms and have different objectives. However, most definitions agree that a mentoring relationship typically involves an experienced (older) mentor who guides, advises, and supports a less experienced mentee (Chandler 1996).

A summary fiche of the intervention on which the example is based is available <https://efforti.eu/node/61>⁸

Log-frame building block_Audience: for Whom?

A first step is to determine the **program participants**. Who will participate in the intervention? Who should benefit from a program?

Determining the target audience implies not only identifying potential beneficiaries but also to **think about their characteristics** and start defining their **needs**.

The audience might be more diverse than initially imagined, including the involvement of external partners such as NGOs or friends and family of the main beneficiary.

EXAMPLE

The starting point of the mentoring program is the high attrition rate of young female researchers. Hence, the **program participants** are firstly young female researchers at the post-doc level and assistant professor levels.

Secondly, the GEP working group also recognize that the university has **experienced staff** as associate or full professors who can share their experiences of successfully navigating their career path within the university.

Log-frame building block_Goals: to achieve what?

⁷ See https://efforti.eu/sites/default/files/interventions/Impact%20Story_AU_Mentoring%20Programme.pdf

⁸ The information provided has been specifically developed to serve as an example for the CALIPER evaluation. It therefore must be read as a 'fictional' mentoring scheme although it is based on the example provided in the EFFORTI database additional material has been provided to illustrate specific points. For example the figure of the GEP working group has been included to make it more relevant to the CALIPER project.

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The goals specify what a given intervention aims to achieve for its program participants and beyond. Goals can be very concrete or rather abstract. However, by making goals “SMART” and dividing them into “outcomes” and “impact”, goals can be made very concise and tangible.

By **outcome** we mean the immediate effects of the program on program participants. These usually refers to changes in attitudes, knowledge & skills, motivation, interests, or behavior of participants which can be observed immediately or over a relative short period of time. Outcomes can be subdivided in **short-term** (less than 1 year) or **medium-term** outcomes (1 to 2 years).

For example, a short-term outcome of a training workshop on “speaking in public” could be a boost in self-confidence among participants. A medium-term outcome of such a seminar could be an increased participation in conferences or public discussions.

By **impact** we mean consequences of a program beyond its direct and immediate interaction with the recipients. The impact of an intervention is broader in scope in terms of affected changes and audiences. A program can have impact across different dimensions, including among others, economic- (e.g. competitiveness), social- (e.g. equality, social cohesion), or technology and innovation (e.g. new services, products, standardization, etc.) impacts. In order for an intervention to achieve impact beyond program participants, its effects need to be observed **over a longer period of time** (3 to 5 years) considering its intended and unintended effects.

For example, the impact of a training workshop on “speaking in public” could be an increased awareness among conference organizers of women experts for discussion panels and more gender balanced expert, peer review committees.

When defining the goals of an intervention it is helpful to make them **SMART**. This refers to: Specific / Measurable/ Achievable/ Relevant/ Time Specific. Yemm (2012) explains how to develop SMART objectives:

Specific (which is where many go wrong from the start and make things too vague)

This step should make things explicit so that there is no room for misinterpretation

The following questions can help to keep this step specific:

- what needs to be done (Express this as a positive, e.g, “We will build...”, “I will save ..” Aim to use action verbs when you can.
- what will be the outcome or result?
- Why is this important?
- Who is responsible? Who else needs to be involved?
- What requirements/ constraints are involved?

Measurable

Many objectives are easy to measure because they are quantifiable and use numbers or percentages or produce a finite outcome. We can track these results easily. The challenge is for the more qualitative objectives where the outcome might be more subjective. With these you need to be able to define the behavioural criteria or evidence which will indicate that the outcomes is what is wanted. (Although not true every time, if you cannot answer the question, “How will you, or others know you have achieved XXX?” it is probably not specific enough.)

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Achievable

Setting the objectives at the right level is a key element. They need to be stretching and ambitious but not so much that they are unachievable- At the same time, making objectives too easy will not be motivating.

These questions can help with this step:

- Is this objective within my control?
- Can I/ we get it done in the proposed time frame?
- Do I understand the limitations and constraints?
- Can we do this with the resources we have?
- Is this possible and practical?

Relevant

Individuals and the team need to see how the objective is relevant to their role and the overall direction of the team. This enables people to see how their work is contributing to the overall organisation objectives. Another aspect of being relevant is to ensure that the different objectives are supporting each other and not creating any conflicts or tensions.

Time specific

Most of us work better to deadlines. This step is about setting the deadline for the achievement of the objective. It creates a sense of urgency required to execute tasks for many people. Deadlines create the focus and help to set priority and prompt action.

There is one simple question:

- When will this objective be completed?

EXAMPLE

The mentoring intervention defined several overarching goals:

- to increase the talent pool at the university, specifically by increasing the number of women in R&I positions
- to improve working environment, specifically the working conditions and work-life balance
- to boost professional capabilities in terms of career planning, networking and professional competences

The GEP working group then specified short-term, medium-term outcomes as well as the potential impact of the intervention.

Short-term outcomes: foster confidence, well-being and job satisfaction of individual mentees as well as improved knowledge and understanding of advancement prerequisites and career strategies and clarification of career prospects and wishes. For mentors, the intervention is likely to increase their intrinsic motivation and satisfaction to “do something good” for a young researcher.

Medium-range outcomes: improved networking and career prospects for mentees through access to mentors professional network. Increased efficiency in time management and prioritizing tasks. Attraction and retention of young researchers. Greater awareness of gender issues in scientific careers.

The following effects of the mentoring program beyond the direct participants and over a longer period of time are also specified.

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Long-term impact: Increase the female talent pool at the organization. The intervention will raise awareness on gender structures at the University and contribute to change organisational structures and culture, including better integration of women in the research environment. Overall, the intervention is expected to improve the quality of the working climate by increasing collegial support, knowledge-sharing, network facilitation and collaboration across seniority ranks.

Log-frame building block_Activities: What to do?

Describe **the activities that will be carried out** in order to achieve the program goals. Participants will have to engage in one or several exercises over an extended period of time. As these activities need to be organized, the design should include an assessment of the required “inputs” and the likely “outputs”.

Input refers to the resources needed to implement an activity. Inputs are usually subdivided into:

- (a) time - how long will it take to carry out the activity? For example, 2 three hour workshops + 2 working days for preparation of the workshop, 1 working day for analyzing evaluation results.
- (b) human - how many persons are needed to carry out an activity? For example, 1 expert trainer and 2 volunteer facilitators
- (c) financial – budget. For example, travel costs for participants or speaker fees.
- (d) material - rooms, consumables, pens, charts, etc.

Planned activities need to be realistic in terms of the required investment.

EXAMPLE

To achieve the planned goals of the mentoring program the GEP working group in conjunction with the Human Resources Department develops a **year long mentoring program targeting 40 young female post-docs and assistant professors**.

The **main activity** consists of **meetings between mentors and mentees**. Meetings last between one and two hours, with five meetings being distributed over the year. Topics discussed include e.g. career opportunities, publication strategies, prioritizing (research, teaching, general workload and work-life balance), as well as project applications, navigation in the research environment.

The mentoring is a **low budget intervention**. Mentors work on a voluntary basis. HR staff is responsible for organizing the meetings as well as initially matching mentors and mentees, organize a workshop to introduce the program and do a limited evaluation of every round of the program.

Log-frame building block_Targets & Indicators

At this stage the WG is asked to try to identify outputs and indicators, which will be then revised and adjusted within the WP4 methodology. For internal use only, it is also suggested to make, already at this stage, **quantitative estimations** of targets related to the identified outputs.

EXAMPLE

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Measure	Activity	Output	Outcome Indicator	
			Short-term	medium-term
Establish Mentoring Program	Establish mentoring guidelines and documents	Published training materials and didactic units for mentors and mentees	Increased awareness about the benefits, opportunities and challenges regarding mentoring program.	
	Recruitment / matching of mentors and mentees	Number of mentors recruited; number of mentees seeking support.	Matched mentor – mentee pairs.	
	Hold training seminars for mentors; mentees	Number of training seminars held; number of participants (gender)	Awareness of responsibilities and duties; challenges of mentoring relations. Adjusted expectations	Experienced mentors; mentor-to-mentor support network; expansion of professional networks.
	Mentor and mentee meetings	Number of mentor – mentee meetings held	Increased confidence, well-being, job satisfaction; improved understanding of career advancement requisites, etc.	Improved networking and career prospects for mentees, etc.
	Evaluate results; challenges and improvements for 2 nd round.	Number of focus groups and interviews carried out with mentors and mentees.	Understanding of challenges and obstacles in mentor program.	Improved mentoring program

Log-frame building block_ Theoretical assumptions and available evidence

At the design stage the section is aimed at exploring the sources that inspired the WG in the adoption of this measure/action. The source can be represented by a publication, another structural change project⁹, the repository of measures elaborated by Smart Venice, etc.

Log-frame building block_ Facilitating & Hindering Contextual Factors

Interventions do not happen in a vacuum but need to be seen within the wider organizational and national environment which is likely to affect its implementation, outcomes and impact.

⁹ For instance, within the project Efforti, the Efforti Impact Story Knowledge Base provides a collection of 17 different types of interventions + their evaluations. The fact sheets provide detailed descriptions regarding the audience, goals, activities, outcomes and impacts as well as monitoring indicators for organizational interventions to large scale national programs. The Impact Story Knowledge is online at https://efforti.eu/impact_story

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An analysis of the wider context also provides important insights on the framing of an intervention – there might be parallel initiatives or previous (good/bad) experiences which need to be considered.

Policy context. The policy context of an intervention captures the wider facilitating or hindering legislative framework of an intervention. This usually includes wider policy frameworks for (gender) equality or diversity but also policy for R&D and Innovation system. Policy frameworks exist on different geographical scales and can range from EU wide, to national and regional policies. For example, the design and implementation of a GEP is likely to be facilitated with references to equality and/or non-discrimination legislation at the national level.

Organizational context. The working environment with its organizational cultures and climate is likely to affect an intervention. These include strategic plans, the organizational goals and ambitions which might be more (or less) receptive to equality interventions.

History / past interventions. Interventions might come in waves or several editions. Past experience and positive (or negative) reception of certain activities within an organization contain important clues as to the likely outcomes and impact of a planned activity. There might be a “fatigue” among participants due to previous similar interventions; there might be synergies to explore with similar interventions.

Collaborations. Existing collaborations and networks with the wider R&I Ecosystem of the organization can provide important hinder or supporting factors. Diverse external stakeholders can provide support in terms of experience, advice, best practice. They can also offer competing solutions – which might diminish the success of an internally organized action. **This section should be well-detailed in case of collaborative actions.**

EXAMPLE

Several contextual factors influence the implementation and the likely outcomes and impact of the mentoring program that was developed and implemented in Denmark.

Policy context. The Act on Equal Treatment, the Act on Equal Pay for Men and Women, and the Act on Entitlement to Leave and Benefits in the Event of Childbirth states that any kind of discrimination on the Danish labour market is prohibited. However, in general, structural gender biases are often overlooked or neglected in Denmark, because the common perception is that men and women are equal and have equal opportunities in Denmark. Simultaneously government, public and private organisations all encourage everybody to prevent discrimination and strive to achieve GE.

Organizational context. A significant influencer is that consensus among leaders and management of the organization to initiate and implement this type of mentoring intervention is crucial (Kalpazidou Schmidt and Cacace 2017; Cacace et al. 2015). Besides the support of the leadership, the case of the mentoring program also points to the importance of bottom up support, e.g. the willingness of tenured faculty to function as mentors as well as the willingness of early career scholars to participate in the program. The university management may support the intervention, i.e. top-down initiated and through financial backing.

History / previous interventions. In 2010 a pilot mentoring scheme was initiated as a collaboration between human resources (HR) at members of EU project WHIST. In 2013, a permanent mentoring program was launched by the University Human Resources Department labelled “Empower Talent!”. The mentoring program was embedded in another EU project STAGES.

Collaborations. Existing collaborations and networks with the wider R&I Ecosystem of the organization can provide important hinder or supporting factors. Diverse external stakeholders can provide support in terms of experience, advice, best practice. They can also offer competing solutions – which might diminish the success of an internally organized action.

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4 Organizing the second dialogues with the R&I Hub

In the GEP design process, a second dialogue with the R&I Hub will be organized in order to expose the overall identified strategy and action plan to the external stakeholders and further discuss about joint actions to be included in the GEP. The dialogue with the R&I Hub will follow the consultation with the middle and top management in order to report to the external stakeholders the strategy and the feasible solutions identified and have their feedback. Here below we provide with some recommendations on how to organize the mentioned dialogues (partly taken from the recommendations provided for the organization of the dialogues in T2.2), which should take place in the form of workshops. The dialogues should be organized by the end of May 2021. Please rely on the experience of the previous workshops in order to make any adjustments to the structure suggested below.

N. of workshops: It is still suggested to organize a minimum of 2 workshops, also depending on the number of participating stakeholders.

Duration: it is recommended to organize sessions of around 2 hours each. It would be probably difficult to engage stakeholders for longer sessions.

Structure of the sessions: the sessions should involve different stakeholders. Ideally the 2 dialogues should focus on different topics/areas and therefore stakeholders should be invited according to the topics/areas.

A possibility could be to divide the topics/areas into two main categories:

- topics directly related to **external relations/relations with the ecosystem:** they would include research/research funding, transfer to market, third mission, institutional communication (its outward component), students services (for what concerns the reach out to potential students);
- other topics related to **internal organization/governance:** human resources and work life balance, institutional governance, GBV/sexual harassment, intersectionality, teaching, students services.

Suggested types of stakeholders to invite: it is recommended to invite all the stakeholders part of the R&I Hubs, both the ones already taking part to the previous dialogue and the ones who could not take part in it. In a non binding way, you could consider focusing on some stakeholders for the two topics: certain entities could actually provide interesting inputs and be potential partners on collaborative actions on both of them (i.e. NGOs, third sector):

- dialogue on topics directly related to external relations/relations with the ecosystem: other RPOs/RFOs, companies (more for the transfer to market/third mission topic), schools, public bodies dealing with research and education (i.e. Regional authorities in charge of ERDF);
- dialogue on other topics related to internal organization/governance: other RPOs/RFOs, public bodies dealing with R&I/Higher Education policies and/or Gender Equality policies, NGOs and the third sector, companies.

Partners can invite the same stakeholders of the two previous dialogues or mix them. The choice of the composition of the dialogues should be made in a strategic way, and according to the outcome of the previous dialogues, considering whether the choice to engage certain stakeholders on specific topics have proved to work or if adjustments are needed.

Based on all the above, it is therefore recommended to try to set up balanced groups and match stakeholders so that meaningful dialogues can take place among them and with the partner's representatives.

More than 2 workshops can be set, if it is preferable to focus on less topics within each workshop.

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As already mentioned, partners should reflect on the results of the previous dialogues and the identified institutional strategy and try to guide the discussion so that it answers the following questions:

- Which external stakeholders seem to be more committed in setting up which joint actions in the short term? with what expectations on impacts and what possible roles?
- Which joint actions identified during the previous dialogues result to be feasible to be included in the GEP?
- Which other joint actions can be identified according to the strategies and solutions set during the consultation with the middle and top management?

Suggested structure of the sessions:

- **brief presentation of the outcomes of the previous dialogues** carried out in the frame of T2.2, highlighting the common challenges that were identified, the strategic opportunities as well as the ideas for possible collaborative actions¹⁰ (15’);
- **brief presentation of the overall strategy** the institution is willing to adopt to overcome gender inequalities, with focus on priorities and main actions, possibly grouped (5’);
- **sub sessions with presentation of the identified priorities, strategy and main feasible solutions per area of intervention and discussion on joint actions:** if participating stakeholders are more than 3-4 it is recommended to set up parallel sub-sessions in order to facilitate the discussion. Each parallel session should involve 3-4 participants maximum plus a representative of the partner institution. The sub sessions do not have to be necessarily homogeneous in terms of types of participating stakeholders. Sub-sessions can focus on all areas or on only a few of them (even on only one of them). Within the sub-sessions enough space should be dedicated to the discussion about joint actions. Since the result of the discussion is crucial in view of finalizing the GEP, it is important to start being more concrete in terms of actions, and also focus the initial brief presentation on strategy and solutions on those actions where greater space for collaboration is expected (1h);
- **plenary discussion** on the outcomes of the working groups.

Partners are recommended to organize follow-up meetings (bilateral or in smaller groups) with those stakeholders with which they are going to start joint actions already in the frame of the first version of the GEP. The aim of such meetings will be to discuss in detail about the joint measures and set up the different steps for their concrete implementation. In particular, within such meetings partners and stakeholders will define the details of the actions to undertake: roles, expectations, impacts, etc. A log-frame (figure n. 2) will be elaborated for each action in a collaborative way (still the use of collaborative tools is recommended) and a dedicated template for this purpose will be shared with the second version of the present guidelines.

It is important to keep in mind that at least two collaborative actions with external stakeholders are expected to be included in the first version of the GEP. Also, in the frame of Task 5.2 “Engaging with the innovation ecosystems: CALIPER FemTech Events”, each partner is expected to organize a FemTech¹¹ Event in M23 and therefore the implementation of such event should be included in the first version of the GEP as collaborative action with stakeholders.

¹⁰ In case the partner decides to sign a Memorandum of Understanding (or other formal documents) with the external stakeholders, its structure and content can be presented during this initial part of the workshop.

¹¹ The name of the event is currently under revision and will be discussed in the frame of the next project online meeting.

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5 Finalizing the GEP

In order to finalize the GEP it is important to conclude the previous steps and elaborate the following documents:

- report of the meeting with the top management (Annex A)
- report of the meetings with the middle management (Annex B)
- a log-frame template filled for each action and collaborative action (see figure n. 2)
- report of the second multi-stakeholder dialogues (Annex C)

The information included in the listed documents will be re-organized and included in an overall document, which will be then submitted to the body in charge to its approval (Annex E).

The GEP will include an introduction of the process followed by the partners for its elaboration, the description of the Gender Equality strategy adopted by the institution, with an explanation of the main challenges identified and coherent priorities set for achieving the desired institutional changes and the list of actions (included the collaborative ones) that will be implemented during the first iteration. For each action a description will be provided as well as all the information included in the log-frame elaborated in the previous steps (meetings with the middle management and meetings with the external stakeholders). It is important also to include a **timeline** for each action. A template to use for preparing the GEP is available in Annex E (provided in a separated document).

It is important to consider that GEPs should be holistic, 'umbrella' plans, therefore ideally cover all areas of intervention¹², and include a balanced set of "soft" actions (typically one-time activities aimed at awareness raising or training) and actions which introduce structural change in processes, routines, rules and regulations. In case the foreseen timeframe for GEPs' approval doesn't match with longer time needed for approving structural measures but the process to initiate such change has already been put in motion, partners can consider to include in the first version of the GEP also those preparatory actions that will allow the change process to move forward.

A first draft version of the GEP will need to be elaborated and sent to Smart Venice by the **7th of June** while the final version needs to be finalized by the **end of June**. Any changes between the first version and the final one need to be shared with Smart Venice in due time, in order to be able to include them in D2.3 which deadline is the end of June.

¹² It is worth to underline that the European Commission has identified, as recommended GEP content areas (in the frame of the new condition required for the participation to the new programme Horizon Europe), the followings: 1) work-life balance and organisational culture, 2) gender balance in leadership and decision-making, 3) gender equality in recruitment and career progression 4) integrating gender into research and teaching 5) gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

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6 Recap of the deadlines

In this section a recap of the different deadlines is provided.

Steps	Implementation of the activity	Elaboration of the reports/supporting documents to send to Smart Venice
Consultation with top management	mid-April	30th of April (report of the meeting, Annex A)
Consultation with middle management	end of April/beginning of May	31st of May (report of the meetings and log-frames, Annex B and C)
Dialogues with R&I Hub	Mid-End of May	31st of May (report of the dialogues and log-frames of collaborative actions, Annex C and D)
First version of the GEP	7th of June	7th of June (Annex E)
Finalization of the GEP and approval by the body in charge	June	30th of June (final GEP, Annex E)

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Annex A: Template for reporting the initial meeting with top management

To be sent to Smart Venice by the 30th of April 2021

1. Organization:

2. Date and place:

3. Participants:

N.	Female/male	Position

4. Brief description of the meeting:

5. Results of the meeting:
 - a. Priorities in terms changes to be achieved and challenges to be addressed : *explain which are the results of the discussion related to the priorities the top management identifies with reference to the challenges/problems identified in the previous steps. In particular, you should mention which are the challenges that are considered as the most crucial and which ones will*

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be prioritized with dedicated actions, towards which expected changes. The priorities should be distinguished according to the different areas of intervention

Area	Priorities (in bullet point)
Human Resources	
Institutional Governance	
Institutional Communication	
Research (or research funding)	
Teaching (for RPOs)	
Students services (for RPOs)	
Transfer to market	
Intersectionality	
Sexism and sexual harassment	

- b. Overall strategy towards gender equality and feasible solutions. *Explain which is the strategy the top management is willing to put in place in order to tackle the priorities previously identified. Here the changes to be achieved are linked with sets of actions and solutions, and an explanation on their casual relation is provided, referring to what existing windows of opportunities the institution can take advantage of. The strategy should be both general and specific for each area of interventions and should briefly explain the steps the organization will take. It will also include a mention of concrete solutions/actions to be put in place, that will be further explored and detailed in the following steps. The discussion about concrete solutions is facilitated by the concept maps elaborated which show the solutions that were identified in the scenarios building task*

Area	Strategy and solutions
Human Resources	

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Institutional Governance	
Institutional Communication	
Research (or research funding)	
Teaching (for RPOs)	
Students services (for RPOs)	
Transfer to market	
Intersectionality	
Sexism and sexual harassment	

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Annex B: template for reporting results of the meetings with middle management

To be sent to Smart Venice by the 31st of May 2021 together with the templates of the log-frame

1. Organization:

2. Number of meetings organized and dates:

3. Overall numbers of participants:

4. Brief description of the overall process followed:

5. Meetings' description:

N. of meeting	Participants		Areas/topics (<i>Human resources, Governance, Communication, etc.</i>)	Solutions/actions identified (<i>provide with the name and a brief description of the actions as well as the external stakeholders eventually involved</i>)
	M/F	Position		
1				
2				
3				
4				

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Annex C: Log-frame – editable template

Tested Assumptions & Empirical Evidence					
(Literature, e.g. http://scholars.google.com)			(Good practice, e.g. RF7, H2020 GEP projects)		
Target audience	Goals & Objectives			Activities	
(e.g. PhD candidates)	Outcome – short	Outcomes – medium	Impact – long	Activities	Available resources (e.g. budget human resource)
	Targets & Indicators				
	Outcomes – short	Outcomes – medium	Impact - long		
Context Factors					
Policy context (hindering/facilitating)	Organizational context (hindering/facilitating)	History (previous interventions)	Collaboration (different types of actions)		

Multi-stakeholder dialogues	Date, time and duration	Number of participants	Number of females/ males	Types of stakeholder	
Workshop 1					
Workshop 2					

3. Results of the multi-stakeholder dialogues

3.1. Overall considerations on the outcome of the dialogues (how did the discussion go? Were the dialogues fruitful? Were stakeholders engaged?)

3.2 Feedback from the stakeholders on the overall strategy

[Report here a summary of the feedback provided by stakeholders on the institutional strategy towards gender equality].

3.3. Feedback from the stakeholders on the solutions identified

- Human resources
- Governance
- Research/research funding
- Teaching
- Students and services to students
- Communication
- Intersectionality
- Sexism and sexual harassment

3.4. From strategic opportunities to collaborative actions

[Report here the main conclusions of the discussion about possible joint actions to set up, providing with as many details as possible. You do not need to plan joint actions for all the areas, but consider that at least two collaborative actions with stakeholders should be included in the first version of the GEP]

Area	Action	Description	Stakeholders involved
Human resources			

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Institutional governance			
Institutional communication			
Research/research founding			
Teaching			
Students services			
Trasfer to market			
Intersectionality			
Sexism and sexual harassment			

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